

Funded by
the European Union

Organisation [University of Évora]
Department [Renewable Energies Chair]

Deliverable 5.2

Final Report on DEC

SALTOpower

Date: **28.07.2025**

Doc. Version: **1**

Document Control Information

Settings	Value
Document Title:	Final Report on Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication
Project Title:	SALTOpower
Document Author:	Dominique Livreiro, Joana Penderlico and Pedro Horta
Project Owner:	European Commission
Project Manager:	Pedro Horta (UEVORA)
Doc. Version:	1
Sensitivity:	Public
Date:	28.07.2025

Document Approver(s) and Reviewer(s):

NOTE: All Approvers are required. Records of each approver must be maintained. All Reviewers in the list are considered required unless explicitly listed as Optional.

Name	Role	Action	Date
Pedro Horta (UEVORA)	PM	<i>Accepted</i>	29.09.2025
Marco D'Auria (ENEA)	PSC	<i>Accepted</i>	29.09.2025
Eckhard Lüpfer (DLR)	PSC	<i>Accepted</i>	29.09.2025

Document history:

The Document Author is authorised to make the following types of changes to the document without requiring that the document be re-approved:

- Editorial, formatting, and spelling
- Clarification

To request a change to this document, contact the Document Author or Owner.

Changes to this document are summarised in the following table in reverse chronological order (latest version first).

Revision	Date	Created by	Short Description of Changes

Configuration Management: Document Location

The latest version of this controlled document is stored in *project folder*.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In fulfilment of SALTOpower¹ Grant Agreement on the obligations of the Consortium towards the Project Owner (PO) regarding project deliverables, the current document stands as Deliverable D5.2: Final Report on DEC, as described in the project Description of Action (Part A).

This report constitutes the final document on Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC) activities carried out within the scope of the SALTOpower.

Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation is an important part of the Horizon Europe projects that all partners must take part in. Communicating European projects should aim at how research and innovation are contributing to an “Innovation Union”.

The initial DEC Plan (D1.3) defined a structured strategy to:

- Dissemination activities (making results public): targeting not only the scientific community but also the members of the 4Helix which might learn/use project results in the advancement of the State of the Art (policy makers, industry, civil society), these actions rely in FAIR and Open Access principles and took place from the moment the project starts producing results, until the project end. Examples of such activities include, e.g. scientific publications or communications, or experimental datasets;
- Exploitation activities (make concrete use of results): targeting the stakeholders which might take part in the exploitation of the project results towards the foreseeable outcomes (e.g. industry in the development of new products and/or services, policymakers in the definition of new regulations, value chain actors in the implementation of new business models), these actions might rely in the Protection of Intellectual Property and take place from the end of the project (or as soon as there are exploitable results). Examples of such activities include, e.g. roadmaps, patents, prototypes, regulatory recommendations, experimental datasets;
- Communication activities (promote actions and results): targeting a widespread audience (stakeholders, citizens) and at engaging with stakeholders, experts, market and public as to raise awareness and show the success of European collaboration, these actions rely on public media (social media, web-based communication, TV, radio, newspapers) and take place from the moment the project starts until its end. Examples of such activities include, e.g. website, newsletters, TV or radio interviews or newspaper articles.

Throughout the implementation period, a comprehensive set of actions was carried out, effectively engaging all four sectors of the 4Helix Innovation Model: academia, industry, civil society, and policymakers. Activities included scientific publications, participation in international conferences, technical and public events, media and web presence and the launch of proposals for further research and industrial collaboration.

Key outcomes include:

- over eight peer-reviewed scientific publications;
- participation and organisation of technical and scientific events;
- launch and maintenance of an institutional website with more than 1800 unique visits;
- active social media engagement with over 1073 followers;
- definition of a Key Exploitable Result and action towards its exploitation.

This plan is divided into 2 complementary components:

¹ Project: 101079303 — SALTOpower — HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-03

- Dissemination and communication activities, oriented to show the attractiveness of the results achieved and their impact towards a target audience composed of key stakeholders already identified;
- Exploitation actions, establishing the main pillars for the market uptake of the results generated in the project, maximising the opportunities for innovation and business.

This report details the activities carried out, the indicators achieved, materials produced, lessons learned and recommendations for the future, reflecting the consortium's commitment to scientific excellence, societal impact, and sustainable innovation.

2. DISSEMINATION, EXPLOITATION AND COMMUNICATION

A fundamental pillar of SALTOpower was the integration of a DEC Plan, which recognised that scientific progress alone is insufficient without visibility, public engagement and sustainable use of results. As such, the DEC strategy was not an afterthought or accessory, it was a core horizontal component, deeply embedded across all work packages (WPs).

Oriented to show the attractiveness of the results achieved and their impact towards a target audience composed of key stakeholders already identified, the Dissemination and Communication strategy of SALTOpower combined online and offline channels and tools, allowing the project to reach its different audiences.

Project dissemination aimed at maximising the extent to which key external stakeholders can use the project's results and outcomes, e.g. thorough scientific publications or communications or experimental datasets, supporting collaboration among key actors in the acceleration of the clean energy transition.

Project communication aimed at raising general awareness and support for SALTOpower activities and its technological focus on MS technologies, as well as their relation to the Green Deal, Clean Energy Transition, and EU-funded research. As a display of the success of European collaboration, these actions relied on public media (social media, web-based communication, TV, radio, newspapers).

Aiming at the ensuing exploitation of the project results, an updated exploitation strategy envisaging a clear definition of project Key Exploitable results has also been developed.

This report presents the final implementation and evaluation of the SALTOpower Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication strategy. It covers the full project duration (36 months), including:

- Objectives and strategic rationale behind the DEC activities;
- Methodologies and tools adopted to reach diverse audiences;
- Actions implemented across all three pillars (D, E, C);
- Engagement across the 4 Helix: Academia, Industry, Civil Society and Policymakers;
- Lessons learned.

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE DEC PLAN

The Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC) Plan defined in the early stages of the SALTOpower project (Deliverable D1.3) aimed to ensure that the project's scientific outputs, technological advancements and societal contributions would be effectively shared, promoted and capitalised upon across a diverse range of stakeholders.

The DEC strategy followed a structured approach to outreach, targeting the four main actors of the innovation ecosystem — Academia, Industry, Policy Makers and Civil Society — across three levels of influence: Regional, National and International. The DEC activities were revised in all the project meetings in order to monitor the accomplishment of DEC objectives.

3.1 Dissemination Objectives

- To promote SALTOpower’s scientific and technical results within the academic and research communities, through peer-reviewed publications, conference participation and open-access deliverables.
- To ensure that knowledge generated by the project would contribute to the state of the art, enabling future research and innovation in concentrated solar power and molten salt technologies.
- To foster collaboration and networking with other R&I initiatives, including those under Horizon Europe, EERA JP-CSP and SolarPACES.

3.2 Communication Objectives

- To raise public awareness about the project’s objectives, activities and expected impacts, with tailored messages for non-technical audiences.
- To use digital platforms (website, social media, email marketing) and traditional media (press releases) to share project updates, events and outcomes regularly.

3.3 Exploitation Objectives

- To promote the uptake of research results by industrial stakeholders, including SMEs and technology developers operating in the energy sector.
- To establish conditions for the valorisation of the project’s outputs, including through Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) management, technology transfer and the creation of spin-off opportunities.
- To leverage project results into future funding opportunities, such as Horizon Europe collaborative projects, Portugal 2030, or regional programs (e.g., Alentejo 2030).
- To develop PhD theses and start-up blueprints rooted in the project’s Joint Research Activities (JRA), reinforcing sustainability beyond the project lifetime.

3.4 Monitoring Objectives

A robust monitoring mechanism (based on KPIs) was implemented to track the effectiveness of DEC actions, enabling real-time adjustments and improved decision-making upon the recurrent update of:

- “SALTOpower_Scope and Success Criteria” (Figure 3.4.1) to monitor Task 5.1 and Task 5.2 KPI’s/targets along with each project meeting revision, and
- “SALTOpower_Social Networks, Newsletter, Website and Scientific Publications”, monitoring the number of followers, subscribers, visitors, visualisations, and downloads, respectively, month by month, as well as the number of scientific publications with the project acknowledgement.

WP5 - Relevant Impact - Lead Deliverable: UEVORA											
5.1 Quadriga Pedia Model impact	ENEA	To maximize SALTpower Widening Participation impacts by implementing Quadriga Pedia Model	Scientific publications	4/8/12 (good/very good/excellent)	1	0	0	0	0	0	
			IP production - patent preparation		1	0	0	0	0	0	
			Scientific and/or industrial exploitation	Availability of guidelines for the creation of spin-off companies	no	no	no	no	no	no	no
				Identification of exploitable results (if any)	no	no	no	no	no	no	no
				IP production (if any)	no	no	no	no	no	no	no
				Creation of spin-off (if applicable)	no	no	no	no	no	no	no
			Regional firm organization		5	1	5	3	4		
			Regional Specialization Forum #1 participation	15/25/25/40/40 (good/very good/excellent)							
			Regional Specialization Forum #2 participation	15/25/25/40/40 (good/very good/excellent)							
			Regional Specialization Forum #3 participation	15/25/25/40/40 (good/very good/excellent)							
			Regional Specialization Forum #4 participation	15/25/25/40/40 (good/very good/excellent)							
			Regional Specialization Forum #5 participation	15/25/25/40/40 (good/very good/excellent)							
			National Energy Strategy Symposium organization								
			National Energy Strategy Symposium participation	15/25/25/40/40 (good/very good/excellent)							33
			International Energy Transition Symposium organization								Participation Day
International Energy Transition Symposium participation	25/50/51/75/75 (good/very good/excellent)							Participation Day			
Attendance to International Conferences		4	1	6	10	18					
5.2 Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication (DEC)	UEVORA	To develop, maintain, and execute a Plan for Dissemination, Exploitation, and communication (DEC) that maximizes the project's results, outcomes, and impacts	Corporate identity established	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes		
			Social Media accounts	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes		
			Social Media followers after 24 months	2000/4000/6000/8000 (good/very good/excellent)	4	4	4	4	4		
			Website established	Yes, with updates	54	405	330	487			
			Website visitors	1000/2000/3000/3000 (good/very good/excellent)	131	656	1162	1582			
			Press releases and mentions in mass media	2/4/5/10/10 (good/very good/excellent)	0	0	0	0			
			SALTpower email	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes		
			Brochures and poster	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes		
			DEC Plan (B1.3)	Yes, with updates	Yes	Updated	Yes	Yes	Yes		
			Newsletter published	At least 4	1	5	7	10			
			Newsletter and contact list subscriptions	100/200/200/400/400 (good/very good/excellent)	62	118	130	162			
			Enredo downloads	10/50/50 (good/very good/excellent)	2	224	321	2062			
											8 writers in the Italian Day; 6 writers in the German Day; International Day - total: 45; external: 30; industrial: 18
											6 writers in the Participation Day

Figure 3.4.1: "SALTOpower_Scope and Success Criteria" file: Task 5.1 and 5.2 KPI's/target monitoring along project meetings

These objectives provided the foundation for the DEC activities carried out throughout the project and are assessed in terms of implementation and impact in the following sections of this report.

4. DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION CHANNELS, ACTIVITIES AND TOOLS

The implementation of the SALTOpower Dissemination and Communication strategy was underpinned by a structured and adaptive methodology. This approach ensured coherence across the three DEC pillars, alignment with project milestones and the ability to respond to evolving stakeholder needs throughout the project lifecycle. The methodology combined strategic planning with practical tools.

Having English as reference communication language, all the contents were translated to the national languages of the partners involved in the Consortium: Portuguese (UEVORA), German (DLR) and Italian (ENEA).

Dissemination and Communication activities were coordinated within the Consortium by a communication manager, coordinating the interaction among the partners, implementing and monitoring the strategy and acting as the main contact of reference for Media and journalists.

From the outset, the DEC implementation was coordinated through a dedicated work package (WP5), led by the University of Évora. Regular coordination meetings ensured that activities were synchronised with the project's technical and scientific milestones.

A detailed workplan for DEC activities, aligned with the project Gantt chart, was defined (Deliverable 1.3).

Coordination of the DEC tasks was supported by online collaborative tools, which enabled transparent access to media assets and planning documents.

4.1. Target audience

The identification of target audiences of the SALTOpower project allowed customising the messages and dissemination & communication activities to every different group.

Table 4.1.1 presents the audience and stakeholders of the sector that have been identified before the start of the project. During the project, partners shared contacts, networking and activities established with these groups.

Table 4.1.1: Target audience and message in different Dissemination and Communication Channels

Target Groups	Specific Message	Communication Channels
1. ETIPs (European Technology Innovation Platforms), IWGs (international working groups) and/or similar fora: in particular, in the field of CSP (concentrated solar power), PV (photovoltaics), wind energy, geothermal systems, renewable fuels & bioenergy, RH&C.	Collaborating to create holistic solutions involving two or more renewable energy technologies will increase impacts.	Web and social media; Press releases; Scientific journals; Events; Newsletter
2. Policy Makers: at the regional, national, and European levels.	Policies that support the development and deployment of MS technologies as part of integrated renewable energy systems will accelerate the clean energy transition.	Web and social media; Press releases; Scientific journals; Events; Newsletter
3. Financial Actors: Examples include the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD) and European Investment Bank.	Integrated renewable energy systems that include MS are financially viable and profitable, and result in a “green label” that is increasingly supported by society at large.	Press releases; Events
4. Technology suppliers and end-users: EPCs (engineering, procurement and construction), technology developers and manufacturers, suppliers, end-users, plant managers, and industrial associations.	Technology suppliers: large markets exist for MS enabled solutions (electricity, industrial process heat, synthetic fuels). End users: MS is uniquely positioned to deliver green heat to the decarbonisation of industry and business.	Web and social media; Press releases; Scientific journals; Events; Newsletter
5. R&D Funding Agencies: European Commission, PtJ & ETN (Germany), MUR & MiTE (Italy), DGEG (Portugal).	Investing in R&I that creates solutions that include MS as part of larger renewable energy systems will strengthen industrial capacities and competitiveness and grow economies at the regional, national, and European levels.	Scientific journals; Meetings; Conferences
6. European Scientific Community: in particular, the European Energy Research Alliance Joint Programmes (EERA JPs).	The clean energy transition requires collaboration among stakeholders from different renewable technologies to develop holistic solutions.	Web and social media; Press releases; Scientific journals; Events; Newsletter
7. TSOs (transmission system operators), DSOs (distribution system operators), and Regulatory Authorities: national and European (e.g., ENTSO-E, ENTSO-G and ACER).	MS can increase the performance and reliability of integrated renewable energy solutions.	Press releases; Scientific journals; Events
8. Global Scientific Community: In particular, the IEA TCPs SolarPACES, SHC, Hydrogen, Energy Storage.	Europe is a global R&I leader in creating systemic clean energy transition solutions that include MS, and wants to collaborate globally to support the clean energy transition.	Web and social media; Press releases; Scientific journals; Events; Newsletter; Fast-Track Schools

Target Groups	Specific Message	Communication Channels
9. General Public: at local, regional, national, European, and global levels.	The general public benefits from holistic clean energy transition solutions that include MS.	Web and social media; Newsletter; Media Forum

4.2 Monitoring and KPI tracking tools

To assess the effectiveness of the DEC activities and facilitate continuous improvement, a suite of monitoring tools was deployed:

- Jetpack² for WordPress: To track website traffic;
- Social media analytics (native dashboards): To monitor followers, impressions, interactions and visualisations;
- Mailing list statistics: For newsletters and targeted updates;
- Event registration and feedback forms: Distributed digitally at outreach and training events.

4.3 Digital and physical tools

The DEC activities made use of a variety of professional tools and platforms, including:

Table 4.3.1: Digital and physical communication tools

Tool	Purpose
WordPress (website)	Website management and content updates
Canva	Design of posters, brochures and social media posts
YouTube	Hosting of video materials
Zoom Colibri	Online events
Mailchimp	Newsletter campaigns
Local/National media	Radio interviews, regional press coverage

All digital content was archived on SharePoint³.

5. DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

The dissemination component of SALTOpower aimed to ensure that the knowledge, methodologies, and results generated throughout the project would be shared widely and effectively within the European and international scientific community. Dissemination was primarily targeted at researchers, academic institutions, technical platforms and R&D infrastructures.

Dissemination activities were carried out through multiple channels, including peer-reviewed publications, conference presentations, training and open access repositories.

² <https://cloud.jetpack.com>

³ <https://teamsites-extranet.dlr.de/sites/EUSALTOPower/>

5.1 Scientific publications and open access

One of the core objectives under the dissemination pillar was to publish scientific outputs in peer-reviewed journals with open access whenever possible. By the end of the project, SALTOpower had produced and submitted eight peer-reviewed articles (seven of them pending publication). Besides that, the project has more than 15 articles in the scope of SALTOpower, but doesn't have the project's acknowledgement.

All publications were deposited in an open-access repository, Zenodo⁴. Metadata and datasets were shared following FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable). An alternative repository (OpenAIRE) has also been considered, though not offering Zenodo's ability of enabling the publication not only of documents but also of research data. Another important aspect is the long-term preservation commitment of Zenodo: once deposited, materials are intended to be stored permanently, as Zenodo is operated by CERN and supported by the European OpenAIRE programme, ensuring sustainability and reliability for the future.

A full list of publications, with DOIs and links, is included in **Appendix 2** of this report.

5.2 Participation in scientific conferences

Another key dissemination avenue was active participation in national and international conferences.

These events provided key opportunities to:

- Present project results;
- Engage in technical discussions and establish collaborations;
- Connect with potential users of the platform and contributors to future research projects.

Participation was tracked and reported internally, with abstracts, presentations and proceedings archived for future reference.

Table 5.2.1: UÉVORA participation in scientific conferences

Date	Event	Location
15 and 16-11-2022	SUPEERA: Bringing research and industry closer	Almería, Spain
29-05-2023	Meeting to coordinate activities in the field of solar biomass pyrolysis/gasification	Portalegre, Portugal
30-06-2023	1st Sustainable fuels workshop	Caparica, Portugal
08-11-2023	EuroPaTMoS Webinar	Online
11 to 15-09-2023	4th SFERA-III Doctoral Colloquium: "Competitiveness of Carnot Batteries in power generation and industrial applications"	Cologne, Germany
10 to 13-10-2023	29th SolarPACES Conference	Sydney, Australia
22 to 25-04-2024	SolarPACES EXCO meeting	Brussels, Belgium
26-06-2024	Solar Colloquium	Jülich, Germany

⁴ <https://zenodo.org/communities/saltopower/records>

Date	Event	Location
19 to 21-06-2024	19th Iberian Congress and 15th Ibero-American Solar Energy Congress	Évora, Portugal
23 to 25-09-2024	4th International Workshop on Carnot Batteries	Stuttgart, Germany
8 to 11-10-2024	30th SolarPACES Conference	Rome, Italy
23 to 26-09-2025	31st SolarPACES Conference	Almería, Spain
24 and 25-09-2025	3rd Energy and Water Innovation & Technology Trade Show	Porto, Portugal

5.3 Fast-Track Schools

As part of the project’s capacity-building effort, three Fast-Track Schools (FTS) were organised in Évora, Rome and Cologne (Deliverable 3.1). These were short, intensive training events targeting Candidate and Young Researchers and technical staff from partner institutions and external organisations.

The events were supported by a structured dissemination plan. Before each FTS, invitations were circulated via email to previous participants and to members of the project mailing list. Announcements were included in the project newsletters published ahead of the schools, complemented by posts on social media inviting participation, and a dedicated news item on the project website.

A total of 122 participants attended the schools, including students of different nationalities from both EU and non-EU member states. Feedback collected from participants showed high levels of satisfaction.

During the events, photos were taken and shared in real time through Instagram stories, helping to engage the online community. After each FTS, a news article was published on the project website, accompanied by social media posts featuring photos of the events, and highlighted again in the project newsletter, which redirected readers to the website. In the final edition, selected feedback from participants was also showcased in a dedicated social media post, reinforcing the impact and value of the initiative (Fig. 5.3.1).

These FTS were designed as scalable and replicable formats, and teaching materials were shared openly online, in the SALTOpower Zenodo and website.

The sessions were recorded and made available on YouTube⁵, using the “as open as possible, as closed as necessary” principle.

A satisfaction survey was conducted after each FTS, and the results will be published on the website soon.

⁵ <https://www.youtube.com/@RenewableEnergiesChair/playlists>

Figure 5.3.1: Fast-Track School Testimony on social media

5.4 Energy Strategy Symposium

This symposium was held at UEVORA with the presentation and discussion of the potential role of MS technologies in the objectives of the National Energy and Climate Plan, as well as of the potential for industrial development and technology exports stemming from the application of the existing/developing Industrial capacity to the technological solutions sought in SALTOpower (Deliverable 4.1). 33 participants attended this symposium.

The event was supported by a dedicated communication and dissemination strategy. Before the symposium, a “save the date” was circulated by email one to two months in advance, followed by a special newsletter⁶ inviting participation. The project website featured a news item announcing the event, complemented by posts on social media and the dissemination of a press release to local, regional, national, and specialized media (Appendix 3). During the symposium, real-time updates were shared through Instagram stories, providing visibility and engagement with a wider audience. After the event, a news article with highlights was published on the project website, accompanied by social media posts featuring photos from the sessions. The symposium was also featured in the project newsletter, and selected participant feedback was later shared on social media, reinforcing the relevance and impact of the initiative (Fig. 5.4.1). Also, the presentations were uploaded to Zenodo, ensuring open access and long-term availability of the materials.

⁶ <https://www.saltopower.uevora.pt/media/#newsletters>

Figure 5.4.1: Energy Strategy Symposium Testimony on social media

5.5 Energy Transition Symposium

This international symposium happened online, covering Energy transition aspects: transformation of the Energy System, Environmental Impacts, Consumer Impacts or Societal Impacts – with invited speakers from Policy, Industry and Civil Society actors.

The symposium was held locally in each of the three countries engaged in the Consortium, with a first day dedicated to local discussion and a second day held online, where the main outcomes from each country were presented and discussed in a joint round table (Deliverable 4.1). Over 45 participants attended the second day of this symposium.

Given its structure, communication was adapted to the two levels of the event. For the national sessions, invitations were sent in a targeted and personalized way, as these discussions were addressed to a more restricted audience in each country. Following these sessions, a news item was published on the project website and on social media.

For the final joint session, involving all three partners, a broader dissemination effort was made. Before the event, announcements were published on social media and in the project newsletter, inviting a wider audience to participate. After the session, a news article was made available on the project website, accompanied by social media posts. In addition, the presentation delivered during the joint session was uploaded to Zenodo, ensuring open access and long-term availability of the materials.

5.6 Regional Specialization Forum

In this context, four forums were held, as mentioned in Deliverable 4.1, which took place in Évora. These forums involved engaging Policy (Regional Development Coordination Commission, Intermunicipal Communities), Industry (Regional Development Association, Entrepreneurial Association, Sines Technopole), and Academia (Regional Universities and Polytechnic Institutes in Évora, Portalegre, and Beja) around the role of SALTOpower technological solutions in the objectives of the Regional Smart Specialization Strategy.

A total of 56 participants took part. The fifth and final forum will take place in October 2025.

Each forum was supported by targeted communication and dissemination activities. Ahead of the events, announcements were published on social media, complemented by personalized email invitations sent to relevant stakeholders, and a dedicated news item was made available on the project website. During the last three sessions, with the hiring of the new communications manager, real-time engagement was ensured through Instagram stories, sharing moments and highlights with a broader audience. After the events, a follow-up news article was published on the project website, supported by social media posts showcasing the discussions. Additionally, the presentations delivered at the forums were uploaded to Zenodo, ensuring open and long-term access to the materials.

5.7 Scientific visibility and metrics

Table 5.7.1 and Figure 5.7.1 present quantitative and qualitative data that demonstrate the effectiveness of the dissemination efforts:

Table 5.7.1: Dissemination activities indicators

Tool/Action	Indicator: Level of success			Achieved
	Good	Very good	Excellent	
Fast-track Schools	15 registrations	20 registrations	>25 registrations	122
Energy Strategy Symposium	15-25 registrations	26-40 registrations	>40 registrations	33
Energy Transition Symposium	25-50 registrations	51-75 registrations	>75 registrations	45
Regional Specialization Forum	15-25 registrations	26-40 registrations	>40 registrations	56
Scientific Publications (with acknowledgement)	4 publications	8 publications	12 publications	8
Conference participations	-	-	4 participations	10

Figure 5.7.1: Dissemination activities indicators and level of success

6. COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

While dissemination targeted the scientific and technical community, communication activities were designed to reach broader, non-specialist audiences, ensuring that the project's work was visible, understandable and relevant to society at large. Effective communication served multiple purposes: to inform, inspire, educate and build public trust in science and technology.

6.1 Communication Strategy

Project communication aimed at raising general awareness and support for SALTOpower activities and its technological focus on MS technologies, as well as their relation to the Green Deal, Clean Energy Transition, and EU-funded research. Communication actions relied on public media (social media, web-based communication, TV, radio, newspapers).

6.1.1 Website

The official SALTOpower website (<https://www.saltopower.uevora.pt>) served as the central hub for all project communication. At the beginning of the project, a dedicated website was created to ensure visibility and provide regular updates on SALTOpower's activities. In September 2023 (M11), the website was migrated to a new platform, which improved its functionality and accessibility. As a result, web statistics are only available from September 2023 onwards.

The site was designed with accessibility, responsiveness and clarity in mind, featuring dedicated sections for news, events, and open-access resources:

- Project overview and objectives;
- General information about the project (e.g. work packages);
- Description of all the organisations' members of the consortium;
- News updates;
- Media presence;
- Materials/resources focused on the media;
- Newsletters;
- Printable materials (brochure and roll-up);
- Links to scientific publications and public deliverables;
- Links to the social media channels;
- Addressing and contact information;
- Appropriate acknowledgement and reference to the European Union's Horizon Europe Framework Programme and disclaimer excluding European Commission responsibility.

The website is available in English, Portuguese, German and Italian, ensuring accessibility to local and international audiences alike. Regular updates kept stakeholders informed of events and outcomes.

In line with the Grant Agreement, the website will remain online for at least two years after the end of the project, ensuring continued access to information and materials produced.

Key statistics from website analytics:

- 1900+ unique visitors;
- 5000 visualizations;
- Most viewed pages: Media and The Project.

Figure 6.1.1.1: SALTOpower website visitors (M11 to M34)

The website experienced gradual growth, but it was precisely in M24 that the minimum KPI for website visitors was reached.

6.1.2 Social Media

Social media was a vital component of the communication mix, enabling real-time updates, two-way engagement and viral outreach. Instagram, X and LinkedIn accounts were created at M4 and YouTube on M11. SALTOpower maintained active profiles on:

- **X/Twitter** - @SALTOpower
- **LinkedIn**⁷ - SALTOpower
- **YouTube** - @RenewableEnergiesChair – SALTOpower Playlist
- **Instagram**⁸ - @saltopower_heurope

Throughout the project, social network X consistently had the lowest engagement and audience reach. Additionally, its follower count was decreasing daily, possibly due to political reasons (Appendix 4). Therefore, during the project meeting #6 held in May 2025 at ENEA, the consortium decided to deactivate this social network starting from June 2025.

Figure 6.1.2.1: Last publication on X/Twitter

⁷ <https://www.linkedin.com/company/saltopower>

⁸ https://www.instagram.com/saltopower_heurope/

Unlike Instagram and LinkedIn, on YouTube, the number of views of project-related videos was tracked rather than the number of subscribers. Since it is less common for users to subscribe to channels in this context, the consortium agreed that video views would provide a more accurate indicator of outreach and engagement. Therefore, even though the statistics tables formally refer to “followers,” in the case of YouTube, they actually reflect the cumulative views of SALTOpower videos.

Instagram was not originally included in the project’s Grant Agreement, but it was later discussed and agreed within the consortium that creating an account on this platform would be valuable. The account was therefore launched, bringing additional visibility to the project, a positive outcome that not only contributed to achieving the social media KPIs but also helped reach audiences different from those on LinkedIn, as the two platforms are used by distinct communities with different purposes.

Achievements:

- Over 1000+ followers across platforms;
- 200+ original posts published;
- Posts shared by partners.

Social media content was scheduled via Instagram, YouTube and LinkedIn platforms, supported by design templates made in Canva and in English (translated when needed).

On YouTube, the project video and videos from the Fast-Track Schools were published.

Achievements:

- 17 subscribers;
- 13 videos;
- 726 visualisations;
- Project Video with 158 visualisations.

Figure 6.1.2.1: SALTOpower social media followers (M11 to M34)

M24

Figure 6.1.2.2: SALTOpower social media followers in M24

Month 24 is highlighted in Figure 6.1.2.1 because it corresponds to the KPI reference point. Up to that month, there had been a steady increase in followers across the different social media platforms, with the minimum target for social media already achieved at M13. This growth was particularly noticeable on YouTube, largely boosted by the Fast-Track School #2 event held in M21, and later reinforced in M28 by the Energy Strategy Symposium, both of which generated significant visibility and engagement. The website also experienced gradual growth, but it was precisely in M24 that the minimum KPI for website visitors was reached.

A list of some social media screenshots is included in **Appendix 4** of this report.

6.1.3 Newsletter and Mailings

Over the course of the project, 12 newsletters were published, with a thirteenth still to be released. These newsletters focused on presenting the project, advertising upcoming events, and summarising key results and outcomes. For the Energy Strategy symposium, held in Évora in February 2025, a dedicated newsletter was sent in Portuguese to serve as both an invitation and an informational resource, as the event was conducted in that language.

The newsletters were published on the project website and social media and sent every two months.

Subscriptions were gathered through a registration form on the website, an existing contact list from the partners and through the consortium's participation in other EU initiatives, events, fairs, workshops and similar activities.

The newsletter has a total of 164 contacts, with seven having unsubscribed. Of the current subscribers, 54 signed up through the website or subscription link, while the remaining 110 were added by the project following events where participants agreed to receive the newsletter.

Figure 6.1.3.1: SALTOpower newsletter subscribers (M11 to M34)

The first newsletter was sent out in M12, although the Mailchimp account had been created one month earlier, in M11. Since there had been no events prior to that moment from which subscribers could be collected, those who subscribed before the launch did so either via the website or through direct invitation.

The subscriber base grew gradually, with the minimum KPI being achieved in M13. At each subsequent event, new subscribers were added, and some also joined through word of mouth, subscribing directly via the project’s website. A noticeable increase was observed from 118 to 132 subscribers in M21, coinciding with the Fast-Track School #2 event in Germany, and a further significant growth from 139 to 161 subscribers in M28, when the Energy Strategy Symposium was held in Évora.

Mailings with invitations to relevant events and other information which cannot wait for the newsletter publication or that cannot appear only in the newsletter will be sent out to the same database used for the newsletter.

Through the use of an online tool (Mailchimp), frequent news and achievements were shared to raise awareness of and support for the SALTOpower action, MS technologies, the Green Deal, Clean Energy Transition, and EU-funded research.

A full list of links to access the Newsletter is included in **Appendix 5** of this report.

6.1.4 Events

The events were one of the most important parts of the dissemination and communication strategy because they allow connections with stakeholders, encourage networking and show advances and results of the project. Events also fed content to the communication channels and tools (website, social media, press releases), generating impacts on different audiences.

The strategy of participation in events will be set up at two different levels:

- Joining events organised by other key institutions/organisations;
- Events organised and promoted by SALTOpower, collaborating with other initiatives and organisations to generate synergies.

- **Presence and Reporting on Key Events**

Partners of the consortium attended relevant events, conferences, etc., like SolarPACES and ISES International Conferences.

International events were one of the most effective dissemination and communication actions to reach the different stakeholders. The partners' participation in events generated more visibility for the SALTOpower project and boosted contact with stakeholders and other European projects.

The project was also presented at international events like the ENERH2O Trade Show⁹ (Porto – Portugal).

Figure 6.1.4.1: SALTOpower ENERH2O participation confirmation on the trade show website

- **Organisation of SALTOpower Events**

As part of the Saltopower project, two symposia and a Regional Specialization Forum were organised.

6.1.5 Press releases and Media

Relationships with the media were established through the SALTOpower communication manager. This task was accomplished at the national and regional levels in Portugal.

Throughout the project, four official press releases were prepared and distributed by UEVORA to communicate the national symposium - Energy Strategy, the presence at ENERH2O - 3rd ENERGY AND WATER INNOVATION & TECHNOLOGY TRADE SHOW (before and after) and about the Fast-Track Schools.

⁹ <https://www.enerh2o.com/>

In the Media

[Universidade de Évora recebe especialistas no simpósio nacional "Energy Strategy"](#)

[Universidade de Évora recebe especialistas no simpósio nacional "Energy Strategy"](#)

[Universidade de Évora recebe especialistas no simpósio nacional "Energy Strategy"](#)

[Projetos da Universidade de Évora em destaque na feira internacional ENERH2O](#)

[Universidade de Évora leva inovação energética e hídrica à feira ENERH:O no Porto](#)

[Évora: Jovens investigadores capacitados em energias renováveis e soluções solares para a água](#)

[Capacitação de jovens investigadores em transição energética e água](#)

[UÉ leva inovação à ENERH2O](#)

Figure 6.1.5.1: Media presence on the SALTOpower website

A press release published in Il Sole 24 Ore (Green Economy guide, Year 2025 – No. 10) and written in Italian by ENEA, the article highlights the agency's work on thermal energy storage technologies as a crucial solution to integrate renewable energy, reinforce energy networks, decarbonize hard-to-abate industries, and the SALTOpower Energy Transition Symposium.

A full list of press releases with links is included in **Appendix 6** of this report.

Impact: At least nine mentions in regional media outlets, including both print and digital newspapers.

6.1.6 Branding, Visual Identity and Materials

To ensure consistency and recognisability, a unified project visual identity was applied across all communication materials. The branding package included:

- SALTOpower logo and colour palette;
- PowerPoint templates;
- Roll-up and brochure;
- Hashtags;
- Social media visual guidelines;
- Email signature template;
- Newsletter.

6.1.6.1 SALTOpower logo and colour palette

The logo represents SALTOpower vision on the use of high temperature Molten Salts Thermal Storage (in orange) as a "hub" for energy storage and final energy vectors inter-conversion: power (in yellow - represented by a plug) to and from heat (in dark yellow - represented by heat waves) to and from gas (in blue - represented by bubbles).

The project also has the logo all in white, black and only the symbol. (<https://www.saltopower.uevora.pt/media/#communication-materials>).

All communication materials used them consistently to ensure brand recognition and coherence.

6.1.6.2 PowerPoint templates

A general PowerPoint presentation was created to align presentations with the SALTOpower visual identity, ensuring coherence in structure, fonts and colours. The PPT presentation was used and completed by the partners of the consortium.

Figure 6.1.6.2.1: PowerPoint template

6.1.6.3 Roll-up and brochure

A roll-up banner and flyers were designed for promotional use at physical events, maintaining the established branding elements.

A roll-up was created using the project's colour palette and the EMSP image, featuring the logos of the project partners and the European Union, the Grant Agreement (GA) number, and a QR code directing people to the official website.

The flyer was designed in a tri-fold format, targeting the general public and presenting the most relevant information about the project. It includes the project duration, the EMSP image, the concept and objectives, the mentoring programme (formerly known as Living Amenities), a QR code linking to the website, the logos of the project partners and the European Union, along with the GA number, and contact details, including another QR code for subscribing to the newsletter via the website. A total of 100 paper copies were printed and distributed at the Fast-Track Schools, Project Meetings, Energy-Strategy symposium, internal events of the widening partner and the ENERH2O Fair.

The design of the roll-up and brochure is in **Appendix 7** of this report.

6.1.6.4 Hashtags

An official hashtag, #SALTOpower was created to reinforce the project's identity across social media platforms and promote community engagement.

6.1.6.5 Social media visual guidelines

Social media templates and visual guidelines were developed to ensure that posts on platforms such as Instagram, LinkedIn, and X consistently reflect the project's brand identity.

Initially, a single template was considered for use across all posts. However, it was later decided that this approach could make the pages appear too repetitive and visually unengaging. Instead, a more flexible approach was adopted, aiming to create diverse posts tailored to each topic, while still maintaining brand consistency. All posts consistently included the project logo and

used the same typography. Two fonts were selected: Oswald, used in the flyer and website, and Poppins, specifically chosen for social media content.

6.1.6.6 Email signature template

A branded email signature was developed to unify professional communications and strengthen brand perception. This signature was used throughout the SALTOpower project's official email communications.

Best regards,
The SALTOpower coordination

Figure 6.1.6.6.1: Email signature template

6.1.6.7 Newsletter

A newsletter design was created for the project, incorporating the logos of the partners, the European Union emblem and the Grant Agreement (GA) number, as well as the project logo. The newsletter consistently followed the same layout: an orange title, an image accompanied by text, and, when relevant, a button linking to the full news article on the website. The design also included links to the project's social media accounts and an “unsubscribe” button.

Figure 6.1.6.7.1: Newsletter design

6.1.6.8 Project Video¹⁰

In November 2024, during the project meeting held at the University of Évora, a short and engaging video was recorded to present SALTOpower. In just a few minutes, the video clearly and concisely explains the project's purpose, combining images of the facilities of the widening partner with short testimonials from each Work Package (WP) leader.

¹⁰ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=YBW9lcAKtL0>

The footage highlights the research environment and infrastructures at UEVORA, underlining the project's scientific and technological excellence. Each WP leader briefly presents their role: from overall coordination, through scientific and technical development, impact assessment, and alignment with energy policies. This format provides a quick yet comprehensive overview of SALTOpower's main objectives and its collaborative structure.

Figure 6.1.6.8.1: Project video

6.1.7 Zenodo Repository

SALTOpower's Research Infrastructure (RI) and Joint Research Activities (JRA) results were presented in peer-reviewed journals and, following the principle of "as open as possible, as closed as necessary," the articles were made available online via Zenodo, a free and open-access repository approved by the European Commission.

Figure 6.1.7.1: SALTOpower Zenodo

The SALTOpower website (www.saltopower.uevora.pt) provides information about the scientific publications.

The SALTOpower community on Zenodo currently includes 73 publications, encompassing both scientific papers and project-related presentations.

So far, the community has recorded around **3400** downloads, of which **72** downloads correspond to scientific publications that include SALTOpower acknowledgement, **215** downloads of the public deliverables published (1.2 - Data Management Plan; 2.1 - MS driven energy system management and power/gas grid integration solutions and 3.2 - PhD Programs), **466** downloads on the papers published and **2732** on the presentations from Fast-Track Schools, symposia and Regional Specialization Fora.

It should be noted that download statistics are only accounted for from M19 onwards, as this was when publications started being uploaded to Zenodo and tracking began.

Figure 6.1.7.1: SALTOpower Zenodo cumulative downloads (M19 to M34)

Figure 6.1.7.2: SALTOpower Zenodo downloads by category

6.1.8 Mentoring Program¹¹

A Mentoring Program was established to support partners, senior researchers, young researchers, and candidate young researchers during their stay in the widening partner's city, Évora. This initiative aimed to provide guidance, facilitate integration, and enhance the overall experience of those involved.

In total, there were 2 registrations for mentors and 3 registrations for mentees, as detailed in Deliverable 3.3.

¹¹ <https://www.saltopower.uevora.pt/mentoring-program/>

6.2 Communication Results

Table 6.2.1 and Figure 6.2.1 present quantitative and qualitative data that demonstrate the effectiveness of the communication efforts:

Table 6.2.1: Communication activities indicators

Tool/Action	Indicator: Level of success			Achieved
	Good	Very good	Excellent	
Roll-Up/brochure	Available online	Available online and distributed in Fast-Track Schools	Available online and distributed at SALTOpower events	Available online and distributed at SALTOpower events
Announcements and Newsletters	100 - 200 subscribers	200 - 400 subscribers	>400 subscribers	164 subscribers
SALTOpower website	1.000 - 2.000 visitors	2.000 - 3.000 visitors	>3.000 visitors	1904 visits
Social Media	200 - 400 followers after 24 months	400 - 600 followers after 24 months	>600 followers after 24 months	1073
Press releases and mentions in mass media	2 - 4	5 - 10	>10	5
Zenodo Repository	10 downloads	30 downloads	50 downloads	3413
Mentoring Program	5 subscriptions	15 subscriptions	30 subscriptions	5

Figure 6.2.1: Communication activities indicators and level of success

7. EXPLOITATION ACTIVITIES

Project exploitation aimed at the concrete use of project results and at strengthening their competitive position as new business/service opportunities. Within the scope of the project, Key Exploitable Results (KERs) were defined around:

1. enhanced collaborations amongst consortium members;
2. expanded networks;
3. enhanced scientific profiles;
4. stronger policy and regulatory support;
5. increased R&I support; and
6. better alignment of R&I activities and funding with industrial needs.

Along the project one main Key Exploitation Result has been identified: the use of the Research Infrastructure as a driver for innovation. Included in the “features” of this KER, a clear vision on how can support to innovation around SALTOpower “beyond state-of-the-art” concept (as presented in Deliverable 2.1) can be provided not only through the upgraded and distributed RI developed in the project (see Deliverable 2.2), but also through further investment in material and technical support to innovation related aspects to be made available to RI users.

For the later, a concrete concept has been developed and is under use along with a financing strategy aiming at the further development of the infrastructure along its lines: facilities for short term incubation, RI interpretative center, investor visits, market and supply chain assessment support, guidelines and documental support to startup funding rounds.

7.1 KER identification and assessment

Following SALTOpower exploitation methodology, covering all the steps required for the innovation process:

- the identification of the problem addressed;
- the assessment of the suitability of the result as a solution;
- the definition of the most suitable IP protection requirements/strategy;
- the identification of a “minimum viable version” enabling its test/demonstration;
- the identification of the relevant stakeholders and;
- the definition of a concrete business model and required funding sources,

a clear definition of the KER and a due assessment of its uniqueness, interest and exploitation route has been achieved, as follows.

7.1.1 Identification of KERs

Along SALTOpower Joint Research Activity, two main work “branches” were developed:

- A. the definition of a “SALTOpower beyond SoA” concept, in Tasks 2.1 and 2.2 (see Deliverable 2.1);
- B. the implementation of Widening RI upgrades and e.infrastructure assets enabling remote and multi-site services with TOP partners’ RI,

both of them potentially standing for KERs. Upon assessment of both options by the PSC:

- “SALTOpower beyond SoA” concept presents the potential for multiple developments at both component, system and service levels, all of them implying the participation of production/marketing enabling competencies (industrial stakeholders);
- the use of the upgraded and distributed RI facilities in support to innovation along “SALTOpower beyond SoA” concept (components, systems, services) entails not only the RI assets but also material and technical support to users in bridging the gap between TRL4-8/9.

This assessment led to the definition of one KER:

“SALTOpower RI as a driver for technological innovation on the use of molten salt technologies for energy applications”.

7.1.2 Problem/Solution identification

Based on the definition of a KER, a clear statement on the problem addressed and on the suitability of the KER a (or the) solution to address it, was validated upon:

- a clear statement on the problem which might be addressed by the KER: what is the problem, how/what is affected, what are the impacts (because PROBLEM, SOMETHING occurs to AFFECTED and results in IMPACT): *“The need for a CAPEX and OPEX intensive BoS enabling experimental validation of new MS technologies and components impairs their validation towards TRL 8-9.”*;
- identification of other possible solutions to the problem: companies developing new technologies, components or services develop in-house testing capabilities representative of realistic operation conditions (TRL5-7), which is only possible to a lesser extent (e.g. small scale components, validation with potential offtaker).

7.1.3 Identification of relevant Stakeholders

The identification of relevant stakeholders is key in the comprehension of how the KER can be turned into a product/service/solution – the innovation process. Relevant stakeholders include not only suppliers (of materials, services, know-how) or customers, but also all other actors which might play a role in the innovation process, as regulators, financial service providers, investors, labour, media, public administration, etc. In SALTOpower KER context, the following stakeholders (and stakeholder matrix) have been identified:

Table 7.1 SALTOpower KER relevant stakeholders

Stakeh.	Descrip.	Role (Influence) [Support]
1. EU-SOLAR IS ERIC	ERIC EU-SOLARIS managem ent and Nodes	Responsible for implementing EU-SOLARIS management and cooperation framework (research strategy, communication, services offer, IP, FAIR data, interaction between members and National Nodes). Ensures GA engagement to widen ERIC’s scope and maintains contacts with complementary ERICs and National RIs. (Governance, services, IP and FAIR data, communication: HIGH) [Widened scope for MSTechs as opportunity: POSITIVE]
2. MS RI Manag	RI managers @ MS RIs	Responsible for defining and implementing R&D and investment strategies, access procedures, technical staff team, and engaging with users and resident R&D groups. (Responsible for individual MS RIs development strategy and sustainability: HIGH) [Opportunity to cost reductions and scope users: POSITIVE]

Stakeh.	Descrip.	Role (Influence) [Support]
3. MS RI Tech	RI Technical staff @ MS RIs	Responsible for O&M and R&D support in each MS RI, holding know-how on MS operations and contributing to reducing OPEX and environmental impacts. (Know-how on MS RIs O&M, critical to procedural changes: HIGH) [Opportunity to share know-how and O&M improvements: POSITIVE]
4. MS Industrial Eco	Industries and Ind. Assoc. in MSTech+ value chain	Industries and Industrial Associations in the widened MSTech value chain (Turbomachinery, vessels, reactors, high-T hydraulics, heaters) holding the know how and industrial capacity to development and marketing of new components/systems (Industrial capacity required to the production of MSTech Innovation: HIGH) [Willing to be part in new markets, regarded regulation is favorable: NEUTRAL]
5. ERICs/RIs	Complementary ERICs and National RIs	Complementary ERICs and other (national) RIs with expertise and RI assets on upstream (e.g. turbomachinery, power electronics, chemistry) and downstream (sector coupling, energy efficiency, grid connection) MSTech fields. (Synergies and widen cooperation strengthening the EU RI landscape: MODERATE) [Perceive cooperation in SALTIS scope as opportunity: POSITIVE]
6. Policy	Energy Transition Policy actors at National and EU level	Responsible for the implementation of environmental and energy policies, regulates the energy market framework, trade rules and implementation of market incentives and/or levies fostering both the objectives of Energy Transition and EU Industrial Leadership and CRM strategies. (Environmental and Energy policy makers at national and EU levels: HIGH) [Define market regulation enabling leveled playfield for technologies: NEUTRAL]
7. Bank/Inv	Financing institutions and Investors	Financing institutions help define bankability conditions for innovative technologies, while investors in new fields are key to leveraging concepts from start-ups or driving investment from established companies. (Actors in acquisition of CAPEX bringing innovation to TRLs 7-9: HIGH) [Investment in innovative ventures, if business case is demonstrated: NEUTRAL]
8. Market	MSTech end-users	Including utility-scale and industrial end-users, define market entry conditions for MSTech products regarding competitiveness with (e.g., with Li-ion batteries) and O&M requirements for swift adoption. (Establish the market pool for MSTechs, enabling their passage to TRL9: HIGH) [Despite early-adopters - might present resistance to new supply chains: NEGATIVE]
9. R&D	Academia, R&D, Technology developers	Natural beholder of the scientific and technological know-how and prone to the development of innovation and technology transfer activities. (Ability to produce innovation but a less to define value chain: MODERATE) [Opportunity for technology transfer: POSITIVE]

Stakeh.	Descrip.	Role (Influence) [Support]
10. Public	Consumers/citizens	Citizens (general Public) act as both consumers and policy agents (electors) with an expectable influence over policies and market. (Consumers perception in the exploitation activities: MODERATE) [Perception of MSTech as environmentally and economically beneficial: NEUTRAL]

The foregoing definition enables us to define the Stakeholders Influence/Support Matrix presented in Table 2.2.

Table 7.2 SALTOpower stakeholders Influence/Support Matrix

Stakeholders Influence/Support matrix		Support		
		POSITIVE	NEUTRAL	NEGATIVE
INFLUENCE	HIGH	1. EU-SOLARIS, 2. MS RI Manag, 3. MS RI Tech,	4. MS Industrial Eco, 6. Policy, 7. Bank/Inv	8. Market
	MODERATE	5.ERICs/RIs, 9. R&D	10. Public	
	LOW			

7.1.4 Minimum viable version

The definition of a “minimum viable version” (MVV) for the KER test/validation as a suitable solution for the problem it addresses includes both the infrastructural assets, but also the material and technical innovation support assets required for an effective support to activities with RI users in the transition of TRL4-6 to TRL7-9.

A MVV of SALTOpower KER entails, thus:

- the RI upgrade enabling the material implementation of services along SALTOpower beyond SoA technological approach at component, system and service levels: as of SALTOpower JRA results in Task 2.3 (see Deliverable 2.2);
- the operationalization of remote and multi-site services with partner RIs: as of SALTOpower JRA results in Task 2.4 (see Deliverable 2.2);
- the definition and communication of an updated list of services: as of SALTOpower JRA results in Tasks 2.3 and 2.4 (see Deliverable 2.2) and of EU-SOLARIS membership (Task 4.1, Deliverable);
- the availability of physical facilities at the RI enabling short-term incubation activities by industrial RI users (as e.g. startups) developing product development, demonstration or showcasing to investors in RI environment: part of SOL4R INCUBATOR and SALTIS proposals (see Section 7.3);
- the availability of guidelines and support materials (templates) enabling the showcasing of products developed/demonstrated in the RI to investors in financing rounds: part of SOL4R INCUBATOR and SALTIS proposals (see Section 7.3);
- the implementation of a virtual interpretation center, enabling the presentation and framing of the RI and RI assets to investors and/or 4Helix visitors: part of SOL4R INCUBATOR and SALTIS proposals (see Section 7.3).

Aiming at the engagement of stakeholders, specific contacts and engagement statements have been defined, as presented in table 7.3.

Table 7.3 SALTOpower KER stakeholder contacts and engagement rationale

Stakeh.	Contacts	Engagement statement
1. EU-SOLAR IS ERIC	ERIC EU-SOLARIS management and MS related RIs (CIEMAT, ENEA, DLR, CYI)	Development of a coherent and coordinated innovation support structure and implementation of multi-site/remote services enables a wider scope of services and possibility of “cross-selling” of services
2. MS RI Manag	RI managers @ MS RIs (CIEMAT, ENEA, DLR, CYI)	Development of coherent and coordinated R&D and investment strategies, access procedures, enables merging individual experiences and open the possibility of exchanging technical staff in peak activity periods
3. MS RI Tech	RI Technical staff @ MS RIs	Shared experience on O&M and R&D support in each MS RI widens individual know-how on MS operations and contributes to reducing RI OPEX and environmental impacts.
4. MS Industrial Eco	(non exhaustive list) SWEP, Kelvion, Alfa Laval, SACOME, Brembana&Rolle EASE - European Association for the storage of energy ESTELA	Industries and Industrial Associations in the widened MSTech value chain (Turbomachinery, vessels, reactors, high-T hydraulics, heaters) are supported in innovation prone to value the know how and industrial capacity in the development and marketing of new components/systems
5. ERICs/RIs	CERIC-ERIC, ECCSEL-ERIC, ESS ERIC	Exploitation of synergies with complementary ERICs with expertise and RI assets on upstream (e.g. turbomachinery, power electronics, chemistry) and downstream (sector coupling, energy efficiency, grid connection) contributes to wider scope of services and approach to interface R&D questions
6. Policy	EC DG Energy, DGEG, MINENCO (non-exhaustive list)	Access to MSTech competitiveness and market pool assessment, drafting their potential impacts on the energy system, provides technical insight into implementation of environmental and energy policies and market framework fostering both the objectives of Energy Transition and EU Industrial Leadership and CRM strategies.
7. Bank/Inv	KfW, EIB, EU-startups database	Access to frontline product demonstration results and participate in the definition of bankability conditions for innovative technologies
8. Market	TSOs (e.g. REN), utilities (e.f. e-on, UNIPER, EDP, ENDESA), industrial offtakers (e.g. BONDALTI, HEINEKEN....)	Providing access to offtaker needs and market entry conditions enables MSTech developers in the development of products suiting market needs
9. R&D	(non-exhaustive list) EERA JP CSP and EERA JP Storage members	Access to reference RIs enables applied research at intermediate TRL4-6 levels and increases competitiveness of R&D funding proposals

7.1.5 Benchmarking, assumptions validation, prototyping

A pre-assessment of the KER's competitiveness framework entails a clear vision on its market framework, on its possible advantages towards competing products/services and on its suitability as a solution accepted by its potential market.

To do so, three sets of activities are to be implemented:

- benchmarking: a clear definition of the market addressed by the KER and of the existing competitors/solutions. This benchmarking should define the boundary conditions for the KER competitiveness: which target users; where; for how much;
- assumption validation: a non-biased validation of the assumptions taken in the assessment of the KER's "selling points". Based on available reports and/or inquiries (e.g. "Mom Test"), a non-biased assessment of the existence of the problem (to final users) and on the suitability of the KER as a solution is to be achieved;
- prototyping: used as a tool to validate assumptions or to engage possible exploitation stakeholders (e.g. those defined for the "minimum viable version"), prototyping aims at testing the KER as a suitable solution for addressing the identified problem.

The activity of benchmarking, assumptions validation, and prototyping within SALTOpower was conceived as a critical step to assess the competitiveness of key exploitable results (KERs) and to ensure their alignment with market expectations. The starting point was a benchmarking exercise that identified the main market frameworks, customer segments, and existing competitors. By analysing reference initiatives and facilities such as EU-SOLARIS ERIC, specialized contract testing laboratories, and innovation ecosystems like Greentown Labs or EIT InnoEnergy, the consortium was able to establish clear boundary conditions for the future positioning of its solutions. This comparative perspective provided insight into target users, geographical reach, setting a realistic framework for competitive differentiation.

Following this, the activity focused on validating the assumptions underpinning the identified selling points of the KERs. This step involved a systematic approach, making use of market reports, stakeholder consultations, and user-oriented methodologies. The validation process tested not only the existence and relevance of the problems to be solved, but also the willingness of stakeholders to adopt the proposed solutions. By doing so, the consortium reduced the risk of overestimating the market potential and ensured that the solutions being developed were grounded in real and verifiable needs.

Prototyping was then employed as both a technical and strategic tool. The applied case of the INIESC-Évora living lab exemplified this approach. Prototyping activities there included component testing, performance modelling, and integrated system validation, all of which will help to confirm assumptions about the solution's reliability, scalability, and economic viability.

By combining benchmarking, assumption validation, and prototyping, the SALTOpower consortium established a process for aligning technological outputs with market realities. This approach ensured that the KERs did not remain abstract research results, but evolved into credible, validated, and demonstrable solutions with clear potential for exploitation and adoption across multiple clean energy industries and has already been in the base of the concept followed in a joint proposal recently submitted (SALTIS, see table 7.5).

7.1.6 Business Model Generation

As part of the Spin-Off Facility, the activity of *Business Model Generation* was oriented towards translating high-potential research results into concrete and sustainable market opportunities. Building on the resource mapping exercise and the identification of innovation pathways, tailor-made business models were developed to guide the exploitation of results with the strongest potential for commercialization. These models were not conceived in isolation, but rather in close alignment with the overall exploitation strategies of each partner organization, ensuring coherence with institutional missions and long-term strategic goals.

The process followed a structured approach that integrated the stages of ideation, validation, protection, and market entry, as highlighted in the innovation framework presented in Palermo. By addressing value proposition design, competitive advantage, proof of concept, prototyping, usability testing, intellectual property protection, and go-to-market strategies, the activity ensured that each model was comprehensive and adapted to the specific technological outputs under consideration.

An illustrative example of this work was the development of the pitch deck for the potential spin-off *INIESC-Évora*. This applied case demonstrated how a business model can emerge from a research-based initiative and evolve into a structured exploitation plan. The model identified key customer segments (including the metalworking industry, solar concentrator developers, battery manufacturers, and renewable fuel producers) and proposed tailored value propositions for each. It also detailed revenue streams, pricing strategies, and partnership opportunities, while benchmarking the competitive landscape against both direct and indirect competitors (e.g., EU-SOLARIS ERIC, specialized testing providers, technology parks, and incubators).

The exploitation strategy embedded in the business model also included a clear roadmap, moving from capacity building in entrepreneurship and innovation (2024), to business model and plan development (2025), market prospecting (2025–2026), and securing the first clients (2026). This stepwise approach ensures that the exploitation of project results is both realistic and scalable, minimizing risks while maximizing long-term impact.

Ultimately, the *Business Model Generation* activity within SALTOpower did not only produce theoretical frameworks, but concrete, actionable strategies that can be directly adopted by partners and spin-off initiatives. By combining internal resource mobilization, international best practices, and applied market-driven examples, it laid the foundations for future exploitation plans that can strengthen the project's contribution to sustainable innovation, regional development, and the European Green Transition.

7.1.7 IP and Knowledge Management Strategy

IP and knowledge management strategy have been based on the procedures and agreements included in the Consortium agreement (CA) and Grant Agreement (GA) of the project, whose starting point has been the background and foreground identified in the CA and in the DoA.

These documents define the governance framework for managing both background knowledge, meaning the pre-existing expertise and technologies brought by the partners, and foreground knowledge, which consists of the new results generated during the project as identified in the Description of Action (DoA). This structured foundation ensures that ownership, access rights, and exploitation routes are clearly allocated, thereby minimizing potential conflicts and maximizing the value of project outcomes.

In line with the innovation stages highlighted in the Spin-Off Facility, the strategy places strong emphasis on the protection of results before entering the commercialization phase. This includes the consideration of patents, utility models, trademarks, designs, trade secrets, and copyrights as key instruments for securing competitive advantage and enabling future exploitation. By incorporating these protection mechanisms early in the process, the consortium ensures that promising results are safeguarded against premature disclosure and that they can be strategically leveraged in business models and spin-off initiatives.

Furthermore, the knowledge management component extends beyond legal protection to cover the efficient organization, storage, and sharing of knowledge within the consortium. Tools for documentation management, feedback collection, and collaborative communication identified in the resource mapping exercise are mobilized to ensure transparency and accessibility of information across partners. At the same time, clear procedures for confidentiality and data

ownership are enforced, balancing openness in research collaboration with the need to protect commercially sensitive information.

The example of the potential spin-off INIESC-Évora illustrates how IP and knowledge management are integrated into the exploitation pathway. Its business model accounted for the need to protect component testing methods, system performance models, and training know-how, while simultaneously enabling partnerships with industry clients and investors. This demonstrates the dual function of the strategy: safeguarding results to secure long-term competitiveness while also facilitating knowledge transfer to external stakeholders under controlled and mutually beneficial conditions.

7.2 The Exploitation Timeline

The exploitation timeline encompasses the actions starting with the identification of exploitable results and ending with the definition of a Business Plan aiming its exploitation, namely:

- Identification of results: exploitable results identified along the project activities monitoring are identified. This stage has been completed by M30, with the identification of SALTopower KER (as described in Section 7.1);
- Evaluation of Business and Innovation Potential: exploitable results identified in the previous step have been analysed from a double business and innovation perspective, bearing in mind the following pillars: Strength of business idea, target sector and competition issues, target market and customers, stakeholders analysis and financial issues. As a result, a single KER with a real potential to become a service has been kept for application of the ensuing steps of the methodology (*see* Section 7.1);
- Product Standardisation Framework: in view of the selected KER, this step finds limited application (e.g. Pressure Directive, Corrosion testing, salt disposal related regulations). In view of the future RI support to the exploitation of energy storage related products, stemming from SALTopower beyond SoA concept, a proper market uptake requires the fulfilment of key regulations, standards and certifications to ensure a smooth commercialisation. In the battery sector, these standards are defined by European or International battery standardisation bodies and can come from the potential buyers (e.g. utilities, manufacturing companies, renewable energy installers, etc.). This activity will be in charge of identifying and informing about applicable standards from a perspective of components, cells, modules and packs. Moreover, the possibility of creating new standards demanded by the market will be assessed;
- Exploitation and Business Plan Creation: an updated exploitation plan and a joint business plan are undergoing. Started in M30, this exploitation and joint business plan has already been the base for a joint proposal (*see* Section 7.3) and is being actively fostered as a post-project activity, aiming at its “embedment” within the business/exploitation plans of each of the Consortium organisations.

The exploitation timeline is illustrated in Table 7.4.

Table 7.4: SALTOpower exploitation timeline

Exploitation action	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6	S7	S8	S9	S10
Identification of results										
Evaluation of Business and Innovation Potential										
Product Standardisation Framework	N/A						Possible in support of new KER along “beyond SoA”			
Exploitation and Business Plan Creation					Base for SALTIS proposal (Section 7.3)		Along EU-SOLARIS, SOLARIZE, SALTIS (when granted)			

Along Project / Post-project

7.3. Exploitation support measures

Aiming at fostering the exploitation of research results by means of the establishment of an exploitation support framework, SALTOpower included a number of activities gathering the best available expertise and resources in the Consortium.

7.3.1 Spin-off Facility

The Spin-Off Facility within the SALTOpower project was designed as a comprehensive mechanism to stimulate entrepreneurial capacity and knowledge transfer across its network of partners. Its starting point was a systematic mapping and diagnosis of the available resources that could support the transformation of academic research and technological development into market-ready solutions. This effort led to the creation of a resource matrix, which catalogued and structured the key assets present in the consortium. These included human resources such as product managers, prototype developers, legal advisors, and marketing teams; financial instruments ranging from funding opportunities to investor networks; physical infrastructures like laboratories and offices; specialized tools for prototyping, communication, and project management; and networking opportunities through conferences, incubators, and associations. The matrix thus provided a clear and organized picture of the ecosystem’s capabilities, identifying how each element could be mobilized to accelerate innovation and the creation of spin-offs.

In addition to this internal diagnosis, the Facility also highlighted international success stories and existing networks that demonstrate effective pathways for bridging the so-called “valley of death” between research and commercialization. Examples such as the MIT Energy Initiative, Stanford Climate Ventures, and large-scale collaborations by ETH Zurich and EPFL were presented to show how universities can play a decisive role in supporting the green transition through spin-off creation. These cases illustrated how strategic partnerships, incubation infrastructures, and entrepreneurial education can significantly increase the survival rate and impact of university-based companies, especially in the clean tech sector. By learning from these models, the SALTOpower consortium positioned its Spin-Off Facility as a platform not only for internal resource mobilization but also for external alignment with global best practices in innovation and entrepreneurship.

To give the initiative a concrete and applied dimension, the Facility showcased a practical example through the development of a pitch deck for a potential spin-off: *INIESC-Évora*. Conceived as a living lab, INIESC-Évora embodies the principles of collaborative innovation by providing real-life testing environments where companies, researchers, and users co-develop, validate, and optimize renewable energy solutions under operational conditions. The pitch deck outlined the main challenges faced by the sector — including high R&D costs, lack of infrastructure, and the need for component integration — and presented the facility’s value proposition as a response. By offering access to infrastructure, component testing, performance modelling, and technical training, the spin-off would not only accelerate time-to-market for clean energy technologies but also reduce costs and risks for its partners. Its business model further identified key customer segments in the metalworking industry, solar concentrator companies, battery manufacturers, and renewable fuel producers, all of which represent growing markets with strong demand for innovation.

Moreover, the example illustrated how the spin-off could capitalize on competitive advantages such as proximity to local industries, direct collaboration with research institutions, and alignment with EU priorities under the Green Deal. With a staged roadmap including capacity building (2024), business model development (2025), market prospecting (2025–2026), and the acquisition of first clients (2026), INIESC-Évora served as a concrete demonstration of how the Spin-Off Facility could enable sustainable entrepreneurship rooted in the SALTOpower project’s technological developments.

7.3.2 Project Proposal Facility

Fostering the sustainability of the cooperation initiated with SALTOpower, the project aimed at capitalising on the results of both joint research and strategy alignment foreseen in WPs 3-4 into new project proposals.

The preparation of ensuing project proposals not only encompassed the implementation of all relevant research and administrative skills developed along SALTOpower but also embodied the base for the Cooperation Agreement and Follow-up structure envisaged in WP1.

This facility structured and put in place the required contents of project proposals, namely: (a) a concrete definition of the research approach and expected outcomes; (b) the design of the work plan; (c) a standardised procedure for the description of relevant background; (d) a standardised procedure for the elaboration of project budgeting - aiming at a more efficient call identification/consortium gathering/proposal writing process.

As an outcome of this facility, along with SALTOpower, different project proposals stemming from the Widening partner have been submitted (or are under submission) after the following typologies: (i) Horizon Europe (involving SALTOpower Consortium); (ii) Portugal 2030; (iii) Alentejo 2030; (iv) Industry services, as summarized in Table 7.5.

Table 7.3.2.1: Project proposals in the scope of SALTOpower

Proposal	Funding	Type	Status (Date)
PS-MSOPERA	BMW	IND	done
PS-ADVIAMOS	BMW	IND	on-going
PS-GLASSPOINT	Private	IND	done
PS-LHEXMS	BMW	IND	under negotiation

Proposal	Funding	Type	Status (Date)
PS-FRAUNHOFER		IND	under negotiation
SCOREFUEL	HORIZON-CL5-2024-D3-02 -11: CCU for the production of fuels	EU	Rejected
SALBIOFUEL	MPr-2023-12	Regional	Approved
H2-Close	Long-Term Joint EU-AU Research and Innovation Partnership on call Sustainable Energy	EU	Submitted (11.09.2025)
SASYFUEL	EIC-Pathfinder Challenges 2025	EU	on-going (deadline: 29.10.2025)
ENCITE	HORIZON-INFRA-2025-01-TECH-02	EU	Submitted (18.09.2025)
TRIGGER	POCTEP INTERREG	EU	Submitted (24.04.2025)
Widening of infrastructural assets of INIESC Évora to AgroEcoFloatPV, Solar Fuels and Power-X activities	ALT2030-2024-25 Infraestruturas e equipamentos tecnológicos	Regional	Rejected as non-eligible to the call (11.2024)
SOL4R Living Lab Incubation	ALT2030-2024-34 Ações Coletivas - Transferência do conhecimento científico e tecnológico	Regional	Rejected as non-eligible to the call (11.2024)
SALTIS: EU-SOLARIS as a driver for the European Industrial leadership in molten SALT technologies for sector coupling and energy storage	HORIZON-INFRA-2025-01-DEV-03	EU	Submitted (18.09.2025)
CROSS-STORE:	HORIZON-CL5-2025-02-D3-21	EU	Submitted (03.09.2025)

7.3.3 ERC Proposal Facility

In the framework of SALTOpower, the application to ERC Grants has been sought as an instrument for exercising Young Researchers in the development of a career development plan, aiming at their future leadership of a research team developing activities aligned with the objectives of the SALTOpower Joint Research Activity (see Deliverable 3.3). Tables 7.3.3.1 to 7.3.3.4 summarize the ERC Starting Grants applications of the SALTOpower consortium.

Table 7.3.3.1: Summary of ERC Starting Grant application by Francesco Aldo Rovense (ENEA YR)

Call	
Applicant name	Francesco Aldo Rovense
Title	External magnetic Field Enhancing Stability of thermal energy sTOrage - EFESTO
Abstract	Sedimentation of nanoparticles presents a major challenge for thermal energy storage systems employing nanoparticle-enhanced phase change materials (NEPCM). These systems use nanoparticles to enhance certain properties of phase change materials (PCMs), such as

Call	
	<p>specific heat and thermal conductivity. However, the sedimentation issue, which is also linked to problems caused by aggregation due to van der Waals intermolecular forces, diminishes the benefits of adding nanoparticles, as they tend to settle at the vessel bottom due to gravitational forces after several melting and solidification cycles. As a result, they are not uniformly dispersed throughout the storage volume. Methods such as mechanical and ultrasonic agitation, along with the use of surfactants, fail to resolve this issue. The EFESTO project aims to explore a novel method to enhance the stability of NEPCM by using a magnetic field to address the sedimentation of ferromagnetic nanoparticles, keeping them in suspension while preventing their aggregation. To meet the research objectives of the EFESTO project, the preliminary phase will involve selecting the most suitable nanoparticles and PCMs exploitable in NEPCM-based thermal energy storage systems, where magnetic fields can effectively manage nanoparticle sedimentation without causing aggregation. Two prototypes of the storage systems, one at the microscale and another at a broader laboratory scale, along with their related experimental setups, will be established to study the behaviour of ferromagnetic nanoparticles in NEPCM under the influence of magnetic fields. Numerical models will be developed to simulate the magnetic field's management of sedimentation and aggregation phenomena and will be validated using empirical data. These models will then be used in the prototypes' performance optimization phase. Finally, the NEPCM samples will be analysed using techniques such as hot disk and DSC/TGA to evaluate their morphological properties.</p>
Requested budget	1,472,120 €
Assessment	The EFESTO proposal was not selected to progress beyond the first stage of the evaluation.

Table 7.3.3.2: Summary of ERC Starting Grant application by Radia El Cadi (UEvora YR)

Call	
Applicant name	Radia AIT EL CADI
Title	"MS-DINAMIC": Design and experimental validation of an upgraded molten salt INfrastructure for experimental Assessment and technology transfer activities on Carnot Batteries: alternative system composition, system Modeling, experimental validation, Competitiveness assessment
Abstract	<p>The research proposal aims to design and experimentally validate an upgraded Molten Salt infrastructure for Carnot Batteries. This involves assessing alternative system compositions, developing system models, conducting experimental validations, and performing competitiveness assessments. The primary objective is to enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of high-temperature thermal storage components within Carnot batteries. By focusing on these components, the research seeks to advance the technology and facilitate its transfer to practical applications.</p> <p>The research will assess the competitiveness of the technology compared to existing energy storage solutions, providing a critical evaluation of its economic and technical feasibility. The project proposal is expected to deliver several key outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Validated Carnot Battery Configurations: Experimentally validated Carnot Battery configurations will demonstrate improved energy conversion efficiency, reduced thermal losses, and enhanced scalability for industrial and grid-scale applications. Advanced System Models: Detailed thermodynamic models, validated through experimental data, will serve as a robust foundation for optimizing Carnot Battery systems in future applications. Upgraded Experimental Infrastructure: The upgraded infrastructure will be capable of testing a wide range of Carnot Battery configurations, supporting ongoing research and development. Comprehensive Techno-Economic and Business Model Assessment: The techno-economic assessment and business model framework will highlight the

Call	
	most commercially viable configurations, paving the way for large-scale deployment.
Requested budget	€2,182,705.27 (Initial estimated budget; will be updated upon reception of the Heat Pump (HP) and Steam Cycle (SC) quotations, which have already been requested.)
Assessment	The proposal will be submitted for the ERC-2026-StG call, which is expected to be open in July 2025, and the assessment results for step 1 are expected by 5 May 2026.

Table 7.3.3.3: Summary of ERC Starting Grant application by Asma Noura (UEvora YR)

Call	
Applicant name	Asma Noura
Title	ZEOCAT-H ₂ : “ZEOLite and Carbon CATalysts from Sludge for Hydrogen Production via Advanced Gasification”
Abstract	<p>This project aims to develop a circular and sustainable process for hydrogen production by transforming urban sewage sludge into both catalytic materials and feedstock via solar/renewable-driven gasification process coupled to possible thermal energy storage systems (e.g., molten salts TES systems). The gasification process will be designed to operate at moderate temperatures (around 500-550°C), which ensures compatibility with molten salt systems and helps mitigate potential corrosion issues associated with chlorides present in the sludge.</p> <p>Sludge will be converted into activated carbon and zeolite-based catalysts, which will be doped with zinc (Zn) and/or nickel (Ni) to enhance their efficiency and selectivity in syngas production. These catalysts will then be used in a tailored gasification process to convert the sludge itself into syngas, from which hydrogen will be extracted and purified.</p> <p>The process integrates thermal energy storage based on molten salt, operating around 500-550°C to avoid degradation from chlorides present in sewage sludge. This temperature level will be used for catalyst production stages such as pyrolysis and zeolite synthesis. For the gasification step, which requires significantly higher temperatures (900-1100°C), a dual heat supply strategy will be implemented: solar-derived thermal energy will be supplemented with high-temperature electrical heating. This combined system ensures the flexibility and thermal quality required to reach and sustain the optimal gasification range, thereby enhancing overall energy efficiency and operational reliability.</p> <p>This approach combines waste valorization, catalysis, and thermochemical conversion in a single integrated framework. This dual use of sludge, as both resource and reactant, represents a highly innovative contribution to green hydrogen technologies. The project includes experimental work (catalyst synthesis, gasification trials, hydrogen extraction), supported by detailed material characterization, process optimization, and sustainability assessments (LCA, techno-economic analysis).</p> <p>The expected outcomes are the development of low-cost, sludge-derived catalysts, the demonstration of an efficient hydrogen production process, and the validation of a scalable circular model for waste-to-hydrogen conversion. The project addresses key challenges in waste management, resource recovery, and clean energy production, aligning with EU sustainability goals.</p>
Requested budget	2M€ (Initial estimated budget: Personnel, Equipment & Installation (Gasification reactor, tubular furnace, GC-MS, BET surface area analyzer, etc.), Consumables / Materials (Chemicals (Zn, Ni), sludge samples, lab supplies, catalysts, gases), Travel & Conferences, Dissemination & Publications, Software, Maintenance, IT, Indirect Costs (Overheads),
Assessment	The proposal will be submitted for the ERC-2026-StG call, which is expected to be open in July 2025, and the assessment results for step 1 are expected by 5 May 2026.

Table 7.3.3.4: Summary of ERC Starting Grant application by Imen Amri (UEvora YR)

Call	
Applicant name	Imen Amri
Title	NEXFUEL: Nano-Emulsion Enabled Thermochemical Conversion of CO ₂ into Renewable Drop-in Fuels
Abstract	<p>The NEXFUEL project introduces a novel thermochemical platform that integrates nanotechnology, catalysis, and thermal energy storage systems (molten salts) to convert CO₂-enriched nanoemulsions directly into infrastructure-compatible drop-in fuels. These nanoemulsions are composed of CO₂ sourced from municipal solid waste incineration, bio-oil derived from olive pomace through pyrolysis (500-600°C), and metal-based catalytic nanoparticles (e.g., Ru, Fe, Cu). Acting as self-contained microreactors, the emulsions provide exceptional interfacial surface area and promote efficient mass and heat transfer.</p> <p>At the core of the system is a custom-designed microreactor operating at moderate temperatures (300-500°C), where controlled thermochemical reactions convert nanoemulsions into synthetic diesel, methanol, and other renewable hydrocarbons. The integration of thermal energy storage systems (molten salts) (280-600°C) ensures round-the-clock process stability. Additionally, the platform supports optional solar-driven redox cycles (operating at 800-1000°C) to enhance CO₂ splitting and syngas generation. To achieve and maintain these high temperatures, the system will incorporate electrical heating technology alongside solar thermal input, providing flexible, high-grade thermal energy that expands the overall efficiency and operational range of the fuel production process</p> <p>Expected Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demonstration of significantly enhanced CO₂ conversion rates and fuel selectivity using nanoemulsion-based feedstocks. • Quantitative understanding of how nanoconfinement and interfacial phenomena accelerate thermochemical reactions. • Development of scalable, modular reactor architectures suited for both decentralized and industrial-scale CO₂ utilization. • Establishment of benchmarks for solar-to-fuel conversion efficiency and lifecycle carbon reduction. • Validation of the technical and economic viability of integrating municipal CO₂ sources with renewable fuel synthesis, supporting a circular carbon economy.
Requested budget	1.5 M (Personal cost, Major equipment including microreactor system assisted with high temperature induction furnace and coupled with micro-GC, pyrolysis reactor, and consumables like pyrolysis feedstock, surfactants, catalysts).
Assessment	The proposal will be submitted for the ERC-2026-StG call, which is expected to be open in July 2025, and the assessment results for step 1 are expected by 5 May 2026.

Regarding a Synergy Grant, the consortium is working on a draft proposal for submission in the coming Call (November'25), with contribution already discussed among the three partners. As an alternative scenario, depending on the successful submission of the proposal, preparation of an Excellence Hub proposal (next Call due in 2027) is under view. Moreover, and following the objective of high level cooperation among senior scientists in the Consortium, an infrastructure related proposal (SALTIS) has been successfully submitted in September'25 (see Deliverable 5.1).

7.3.4 Other exploitation supporting events

UEVORA took part in the 3rd edition of ENERH2O – Energy & Water Innovation & Technology Trade Show, held on September 24–25, 2025, at Exponor, in Porto.

The SALTOpower and Sol2H2O projects, coordinated by the University of Évora, played a prominent role, showcasing cutting-edge work in the field of solar energy for the water-energy nexus and in molten salt technologies for energy applications. This participation proved valuable, as it allowed for the dissemination of the work carried out, the establishment of contacts with companies and professionals in the sector, and the opening of paths for potential future synergies that strengthen the link between research and the market.

Within the conference program, the coordinator of the SOL4R unit, Pedro Horta, delivered a talk dedicated to the topics “Sol2H2O: The potential role of Solar Energy in the Water-Energy Nexus” and “Molten Salt technologies as an Energy Hub for the Energy Transition,” related to both projects, where he also presented the National Research Infrastructure in Concentrated Solar Power (INIESC) and the innovative activities of SOL4R at the Mitra Campus in Évora. He also took part in the session promoted by the Alliance for the Energy Transition, contributing to the debate on green hydrogen and its role in the energy transition.

Figure 7.3.4.1: 3rd edition of ENERH2O – Energy & Water Innovation & Technology Trade Show

8. LESSONS LEARNED / CONCLUSIONS

Throughout the implementation of SALTOpower, the strategy for Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC) proved to be fundamental to ensuring the project’s impact across academia, industry, policy makers and civil society. The methodology adopted was conceived within the framework of the Quadruple Helix model and unfolded at three levels - regional, national and international - in order to maximise outreach and visibility of results. Moreover, the plan was structured into different phases: an initial phase focused on the creation of the visual identity and communication tools; a second phase, dedicated to the first dissemination of results, particularly those linked to the Fast-Track Schools; a third phase, centred on wider dissemination through symposia and regional forums; and, finally, an impact phase, taking place after the formal end of the project, with the website remaining active for at least two years and all public deliverables and publications being made openly available through Zenodo, the project site and the social media channels.

In terms of indicators, several KPIs were established to monitor the implementation of the strategy, including the number of participants registered in scientific and industrial events, the

number of visits to the website, the volume of social media followers, the subscription rate to the newsletter, and the number of press releases or media coverage achieved. These KPIs were useful for tracking progress, but they also revealed important limitations. On the one hand, they focused predominantly on quantitative metrics, such as “number of followers” or “number of views”, which do not necessarily reflect the quality of engagement with target audiences. On the other hand, the definition of success based on absolute thresholds, such as reaching a given number of followers, was not always suitable for a highly specialised project with relatively narrow but very qualified audiences. A richer assessment could have included qualitative indicators, such as the number of citations of project deliverables in scientific literature and policy documents, downloads segmented by categories on Zenodo, or invitations received by the partners to take part in international working groups.

The Dissemination and Communication KPIs were all achieved, at least at the “Good” level and the “Excellent” several times, which indicates a good effort from the Widening partner with the support of the TOP partners.

The experience with social media represents another important area of reflection. While the project maintained a presence on different platforms, it became clear that Twitter/X did not add significant value, both because of the decline of its user base in Europe and Portugal, and because its short and fast-paced communication style was ill-suited to the project’s content. Instagram, although very popular in Portugal and across Europe, also proved inadequate, since the project does not “live by images” and its target audiences are not primarily present on that platform. Nonetheless, an interesting pattern was observed: posts that included faces or project members had greater reach, especially when they were reshared by the researchers themselves on their personal *stories*, suggesting the importance of humanising scientific communication. By contrast, more technical or institutional posts attracted far less attention. LinkedIn, on the other hand, proved to be the most appropriate social network for the project, clearly aligning with the key audiences of researchers, industry and policy makers.

Another lesson learned relates to the internal organisation of communication. Since support from the institutional communication department was not available, a dedicated professional was hired to ensure consistency and continuity. This solution proved highly effective and illustrates the importance of specialised human resources in managing communication for European projects. In parallel, the decision to upload public presentations and deliverables in categories on Zenodo turned out to be strategic, significantly increasing the number of downloads and extending the project’s visibility beyond the initial expectations, which had been mostly limited to scientific articles. However, if counting only the downloads of scientific publications with the SALTOpower acknowledgement the “Excellent” KPI was still achieved.

All the target audiences identified at the beginning of the project (ETIPs and international fora, policy makers, financial actors, technology suppliers and end-users, R&D funding agencies, the European and global scientific communities, TSOs/DSOs/regulators, and the general public) were reached through a mix of tailored communication channels. The most significant evidence of impact, however, was observed within academia and the scientific community, as well as among industrial stakeholders, particularly technology developers, suppliers and end-users who engaged with the project’s outputs and recognized the potential of MS-based solutions. Policy makers were also exposed to the results through events and publications, though the translation into concrete policy measures remained more difficult to measure, while financial actors and funding agencies engaged only at a more limited scale.

By contrast, penetration into civil society - represented in the table as the general public - was more modest, despite the use of newsletters, online media and public forums. This underlines the importance of developing more accessible and relatable narratives, connecting MS technologies to citizens’ everyday concerns such as affordability, energy security and climate action. Strengthening this dimension in future initiatives will be key to complement the stronger results already achieved with academia, industry and policy-oriented groups.

The main lessons that emerge from this process can therefore be summarised along four axes. First, KPIs must be tailored to the nature of the project, prioritizing qualitative and impact-oriented measures over absolute numbers. Second, social media platforms must be carefully selected, not on the basis of general popularity but on their alignment with the project's real target audiences. Third, researchers must play an active role in dissemination, leveraging their own personal and professional networks to increase reach. Finally, the project demonstrated the importance of showing the people behind the science, since these posts consistently attracted greater attention than purely technical content.

In conclusion, SALTOpower showed that communicating science requires careful planning, dedicated resources and appropriate metrics, but also flexibility to adapt methodologies to the responses of target audiences. The legacy it leaves goes beyond the scientific component: it represents a set of valuable lessons on how communication, dissemination and exploitation can become strategic pillars as important as research itself.

9. RELATED PLANS (FOLLOWING PM² METHODOLOGY)

Deliverables Acceptance Plan

The management of the formal customer's acceptance of project deliverables (responsibilities, activities and the criteria for the deliverables acceptance) is described in the *Deliverables Acceptance Plan*. The location of this artefact is found in Appendix 1.

Project Description of Action

The *Project Description of Action* includes the project Work Plan and captures all types of resource requirements, schedule and effort/costs foreseen for the deliverables acceptance activities. The location of this artefact is found in Appendix 1.

Data Management Plan

The *Data Management Plan* describes the data management life cycle for the data to be collected, processed and/or generated in a project. The location of this artefact is found in Appendix 1.

Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan

The *Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan* describes the DEC activities foreseen for the project. The location of this artefact is found in Appendix 1.

APPENDIX 1: REFERENCES AND RELATED DOCUMENTS

The Project documents will be stored in a shared drive located on the DLR server in Germany. The access will be granted by that partner, and each user will have a different access according to their profile, role and responsibility in the project.

The Project Steering Committee (PSC) will have access and editing permissions to all folders in the drive. The Project Core Team (PCT) will have editing access to respective WP folders and reading access to the remaining ones. The Project Support Team (PST) will have reading access to WP folders, and finally, the Project Owner (PO) may have reading access to all folders, including legal documents.

In each folder, the latest PDF and Word versions of each document will be available, and the previous versions shall be conserved in a separate folder named [versions] until the end of the project.

At the end of the project, each partner will make a copy of the shared folder to be stored in their own organisation's drive, and this must be kept following internal organisational procedures.

ID	Reference or <Related Document>	Source or <Link/Location>
1	Project folder	
2	Project Description of Action (Part A) <101079303_Annex 1 - Description of the action (part A).pdf>	Project folder
3	Project Description of Action (Part B) <101079303_Annex 1 - Description of the action (part B).pdf>	Project folder
4	Deliverables Acceptance Plan <[08.I.PM2.v3].Deliverables_Acceptance_Plan.SALTOPOWER.14-02-2023.v.1>	Project Folder
5	Deliverables Acceptance Checklist	Project Folder
6	Data Management Plan <SALTOPOWER_D_1_2_DATA_MANAGEMENT_PLAN_05-05-2023_v_2>	Project Folder
7	Scope and Success Criteria <SALTOpower_Scope and Success Criteria_v1>	Project Folder
8	Social networks, Newsletter, Website, and Scientific Publications <SALTOpower_Social networks, Newsletter, Website, and Scientific Publications>	Project Folder
9	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan <SALTOPOWER_D_1_3_DEC_PLAN_13-09-2023_v_2>	Project Folder

APPENDIX 2: SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS

Scientific Publication	DOI	Link in Zenodo	SALTOpower Acknowledgement
Comparison of Parabolic Troughs and Solar Photovoltaic as Solar Field Technology in Dispatchable Solar Power Plants: A Competitiveness Assessment Horta, P., Eusébio, T., Santos, A., Cadi, R., & Fialho, L. (2024). SolarPACES 2023	https://doi.org/10.52825/solarpac.es.v2i.751	https://zenodo.org/records/13737038	Yes
Solar Driven Syngas Production Potential in Portugal. SolarPACES Conference Proceedings Horta, P., Canavarro, D., Camilo-Alves, C., Brito, P., & Panizio, R. (2024)	https://doi.org/10.52825/solarpac.es.v2i.750	https://zenodo.org/records/14588588	No
Optimização Económica da Operação de Armazenamento Térmico a Sais Fundidos com Pirólise de Biomassa: um estudo para a região do Alentejo, CIES 2024 Conference Pires, C., Felizardo, F., Mané, J., Malico, I., Horta, P.	Waiting for DOI		No
A infraestrutura INIESC no contexto da EU-SOLARIS: Actividades e perspectivas futuras, CIES 2024 Conference Horta, P., Canavarro, D., Cardoso, J., Azevedo, P., Martinez, D.	Waiting for DOI		Yes
Avaliação da Competitividade de Configurações Tecnológicas de Centrais Solares com Armazenamento no Espaço Iberoamericano, CIES 2024 Conference Eusebio, T., Cadi, R., Horta, P.	Waiting for DOI		No
A Utilização de Sais Fundidos como Material de Armazenamento Térmico em Baterias de Carnot, CIES 2024 Conference Cadi, R., Eusebio, T., Horta, P.	Waiting for DOI		No
Heat Supply to Industrial Processes via Molten Salt Solar Concentrators, Energies 2024, 17, 4541. D'Auria, M.; Grena, R.; Lanchi, M.; Liberatore, R. Energies 2024, 17, 4541.	https://doi.org/10.3390/en17184541	https://zenodo.org/records/15411932	Yes
Comparative Techno-economic Analysis of Different Parabolic	https://doi.org/10.52825/solarpac	https://zenodo.org/records/17225125	Yes

Scientific Publication	DOI	Link in Zenodo	SALTOpower Acknowledgement
<p>Trough CSP Plants for the Italian Market.</p> <p>Oral presentation in SolarPACES 2024, full paper submitted and under revision.</p> <p>Walter Gaggioli, Marco D'Auria, Valeria Russo, Simona De Iulii, Luca Turchetti, Jürgen Dersch, Michael Wittmann, Tobias Hirsch, Jana Stengler.</p>	ces.v3i.2477		
<p>Molten Salt Mixtures as an Energy Carrier for Thermochemical Processes of Renewable Gas Production: Review and Perspectives</p> <p>Appl. Sci. 2025, 15, 6916.</p> <p>D'Auria, M.; Tizzoni, A.C.; Rovense, F.; Sau, S.; Turchetti, L.; Canavarro, D.; Marchã, J.; Horta, P.; Lanchi, M.</p>	https://doi.org/10.3390/app15126916	HTTPS://ZENODO.ORG/RECORDS/17140253	Yes
<p>Understanding the effect of oxide ions on Solar Salt chemistry and corrosion mechanism of 316 L stainless steel at 600 °C</p> <p>Kumar, S., Swaminathan, S., Hesse, R., Goldbeck, H., Ding, W., Bonk, A., Bauer, T.</p>	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.corsci.2025.112849	https://zenodo.org/records/15395114	No
<p>Zero-emission chemical sites – combining power purchase agreements with thermal energy storage</p> <p>Klasing, F., Prenzel, M., Kirschbaum, S., Bauer, T.</p>	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2025.115667	https://zenodo.org/records/15395345	No
<p>Repurposing of supercritical coal plants into highly flexible grid storage with adapted 620 °C nitrate salt technology</p> <p>Klasing, F., Prenzel, M., Bauer, T.</p>	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2024.124524	https://zenodo.org/records/15395530	No
<p>Critical diameter for a single-tank molten salt storage – Parametric study on structural tank design</p> <p>Creators</p> <p>Klasing, F., Schmitz, M., Gerdes, C., Odenthal, C., Bauer, T.</p>	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2024.113870	https://zenodo.org/records/15396415	No
<p>Corrosion characteristics of 316L stainless steel in oxide-rich molten solar salt at 600 °C</p> <p>Creators</p> <p>Swaminathan, S., Sumit, K., Kranzmann, A., Hesse, R., Goldbeck, H., Fantin, A.</p>	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solmat.2024.113176	https://zenodo.org/records/15396469	No
<p>Influence of atmosphere and austenitic stainless steel on the solar salt corrosivity</p> <p>Kumar, S., Hanke, A., Bonk, A., Bauer, T.</p>	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e25966	https://zenodo.org/records/15396521	No

Scientific Publication	DOI	Link in Zenodo	SALTOpower Acknowledgement
The Potential of Thermal Energy Storage for Sustainable Energy Supply at Chemical Sites Prenzel, M., Klasing, F., Rüdiger, F., Perry, K., Juliane, T., Reimer, A., Stefan, K., Bauer, T.	https://doi.org/10.2991/978-94-6463-156-2_25	https://zenodo.org/records/15396853	No
Molten chloride salt technology for next-generation CSP plants: Selection of cold tank structural material utilizing corrosion control at 500°C Qing, G., Hanke, A., Kessel, F., Bonk, A., Ding, W., Bauer, T.	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solmat.2023.112233	https://zenodo.org/records/15397016	No
Comparative study of models for packed bed molten salt storage systems Odenthal, C., Tombrink, J., Klasing, F., Bauer, T.	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2023.120245	https://zenodo.org/records/15408330	No
Concentrating solar power at higher limits: First studies on molten nitrate salts at 600 °C in a 100 kg-scale hot tank Kunkel, S., Klasing, F., Hanke, A., Bauer, T., Bonk, A.	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solmat.2023.112412	https://zenodo.org/records/15411479	No
Corrosion behavior of Fe-Cr-Ni based alloys exposed to molten MgCl ₂ -KCl-NaCl salt with over-added Mg corrosion inhibitor Yu, R., Gong, Q., Shi, H., Chai, Y., Bonk, A., Weisenburger, A., Wang, D., Müller, G., Bauer, T., Ding, W.	https://doi.org/10.1007/s11705-023-2349-1	https://zenodo.org/records/15411648	No
Solar Salt above 600 °C: Impact of Experimental Design on Thermodynamic Stability Results Steinbrecher, J., Braun, M., Bauer, T., Kunkel, S. Bonk, A.	https://doi.org/10.3390/en16145241	https://zenodo.org/records/15411721	No
Stabilization of Solar Salt at 650°C – Thermodynamics and practical implications for thermal energy storage systems Steinbrecher, J., Hanke, A., Braun, M., Bauer, T., Bonk, A.	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solmat.2023.112411	https://zenodo.org/records/15411778	No
Effect of gas management on corrosion resistance in molten solar salt up to 620°C: Corrosion of SS316-types and SS347 https://doi.org/10.1016/j.corsci.2023.111700	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.corsci.2023.111700	https://zenodo.org/records/15411875	No
Thermal stability investigation of molten salt mixtures for CSP applications. Presented as poster 30th SolarPACES24 Francesco Rovense, Davide Pasqualitto, Anna Chiara Tizzoni, Salvatore Sau, Valeria Russo,	Waiting for DOI		Yes

Scientific Publication	DOI	Link in Zenodo	SALTOpower Acknowledgement
Elisabetta Veca, Natale Corsaro, Negin Roshan, Matteo Battaglia, Annarita Spadoni, Silvia Licocchia and Paolo Venturini			
<p>Molten Salt Technology as a Flexible Solution for Power-Gas Interconnection</p> <p>Presented as poster in 31st SolarPACES 2025</p> <p>Marco D'Auria, Anna Chiara Tizzoni, Luca Turchetti, Michela Lanchi, Diogo Canavarro, João Marchã, Radia Ait El Cadi, Tiago Eusebio, Paula Martins, Thomas Bauer, Eckhard Lüpfer, Pedro Horta and Simona De Iulii</p>	Waiting for DOI		Yes
<p>Molten Salt Technology as a Flexible Solution for Power-Gas Interconnection</p> <p>Submitted as conference proceeding on 25th September 2025</p> <p>Marco D'Auria, Anna Chiara Tizzoni, Salvatore Sau, Luca Turchetti, Michela Lanchi, Diogo Canavarro, João Marchã, Radia Ait El Cadi, Tiago Eusebio, Paula Martins, Thomas Bauer, Eckhard Lüpfer, Pedro Horta, Simona De Iulii</p>	Waiting for DOI		Yes

APPENDIX 3: ENERGY STRATEGY SYMPOSIUM

Communication and dissemination made before, after and during the Energy Strategy Symposium, held in Évora.

- Save the date via email

Exmos. Senhores e Senhoras,

no âmbito do projeto **Twinning HEUROPE SALTpower**, coordenado pela **Universidade de Évora** e com a participação da Agência Aeroespacial Alemã (**DLR**) e da Agência Italiana para a Energia Nuclear e Renováveis (**ENEA**), na sequência dos Fóruns de Especialização Regional, vamos organizar o **simpósio nacional Energy Strategy**. Focado na discussão com atores regionais e nacionais, o ESSymp tem o objetivo de apresentar e discutir o papel potencial das tecnologias de Sal Fundido nos objetivos do Plano Nacional de Energia e Clima, bem como o potencial de desenvolvimento industrial e exportação de tecnologia decorrente da aplicação da capacidade industrial existente/em desenvolvimento às soluções tecnológicas procuradas no SALTpower.

Temos o gosto de os convidar a participar neste simpósio que irá decorrer em Évora (evento presencial, com visita à infraestrutura de investigação), no dia **13 de Fevereiro de 2025** -> **SAVE THE DATE!**

Brevemente, disponibilizaremos a agenda e formulário de inscrição.

Esperamos contar com a vossa presença,
votos de Boas Festas!

A coordenação SALTpower

- Website publication¹² before the symposium

¹² <https://www.saltpower.uevora.pt/energy-strategy-symposium/>

- Special invitation newsletter for the symposium¹³

- Press release sent before the symposium

Universidade de Évora recebe especialistas do setor da energia no simpósio nacional "Energy Strategy"

Évora, 3 de fevereiro de 2025 – A Universidade de Évora será palco, no próximo dia 13 de fevereiro, do simpósio nacional "Energy Strategy", promovido pela Cátedra de Energias Renováveis no âmbito do projeto europeu [SALTOpower](#).

Este projeto resulta de uma parceria entre a Universidade de Évora, a Agência Aeroespacial Alemã (DLR) e a Agência Italiana para a Energia Nuclear e Renováveis (ENEA).

O evento reunirá especialistas, decisores políticos, investigadores e representantes da indústria para debater o impacto das tecnologias de Sais Fundidos para aplicações no setor energético. O objetivo é promover uma reflexão sobre o potencial contributo destas tecnologias para os objetivos do Plano Nacional de Energia e Clima, o desenvolvimento industrial e o crescimento de exportações associadas à sua implementação.

As atividades terão início às 09h15, na Casa Cordovil da Universidade de Évora. Durante a tarde, os participantes terão a oportunidade de visitar a Évora Molten Salt Platform, no pólo de Évora da INIESC (Infraestrutura Nacional de Investigação em Energia Solar de Concentração). Esta infraestrutura integra o Consórcio Europeu de Infraestrutura de Investigação ERIC EU-SOLARIS e é um centro de excelência em investigação e desenvolvimento de tecnologias de sais fundidos.

Informações sobre o Evento

Data: 13 de fevereiro de 2025

Hora: 9h15

Local: Casa Cordovil, Universidade de Évora, Évora
(<https://maps.app.goo.gl/DLx3vTe29B6znqr16>)

Évora Molten Salt Platform (<https://maps.app.goo.gl/3hqvRp3GkVB1QQL46>)

Para obter mais informações, por favor contacte:

Joana Mouquinho Penderlico - joana.penderlico@uevora.pt

Dominique Livreiro - dominique.livreiro@uevora.pt

¹³ <https://mailchi.mp/d1a49c317bec/newsletter-14171674>

- Instagram¹⁴ with publications before and after the symposium (the same were made on LinkedIn¹⁵)

¹⁴ https://www.instagram.com/saltopower_heurope/

¹⁵ <https://www.linkedin.com/company/saltopower>

- Website publication¹⁶ after the symposium

The screenshot shows the SALTOpower website with a navigation bar at the top containing 'The Project', 'Research', 'Careers', 'Media', 'Access', and 'Contacts'. The main headline reads: **“Energy Strategy” Symposium brings together experts to discuss the future**. Below the headline is the date 17/02/2025 and a sub-headline: **The event brought together experts, policymakers, researchers and industry representatives to discuss the impact of Molten Salt Technologies**. A photograph shows a group of approximately 20 people standing in a line outdoors in front of a building. Below the photo, the text states: **The portuguese symposium “Energy Strategy,” organized by the Renewable Energies Chair of the University of Évora under the European project SALTOpower, successfully took place on February 13. The event brought together experts, policymakers, researchers, and industry representatives to discuss the impact of Molten Salt Technologies on the energy sector.** Further text describes the event's location at Casa Cordovil, its focus on presentations and debates, and the opportunity for participants to visit the Évora Molten Salt Platform. It concludes by stating that the symposium served as a platform for dialogue and reflection on innovations and challenges in the energy sector.

¹⁶ www.saltopower.uevora.pt/energy-strategy-symposium-brings-together-experts-at-evora-to-discuss-the-future/

APPENDIX 4: SOCIAL MEDIA

- X - Number of followers decreasing

Date	LinkedIn	X
M1 - nov 2022		
M2		
M3		
M4		0
M5		
M6	12	
M7	34	
M8	41	
M9	34	
M10 - aug 2023	41	
M11	47	3
M12	61	3
M13 - nov 2023	64	4
M14	71	6
M15		
M16 - feb 2024	104	42
M17	131	42
M18	171	56
M19	191	56
M20 - jun 2024	204	64
M21	211	60
M22	211	65
M23	221	58
M24 - out 24	231	57
M25	241	33
M26	241	14
M27	251	14
M28	251	13
M29	261	12
M30 - apr 2025	261	12
M31	261	12
M32	271	0
M33	271	0
M34	271	0
M35		
M36 - oct 2025		

- LinkedIn

SALTOpower
European Facility on Molten SALT technologies
10 power and energy system applications
GA Number: 101075302
European Research Executive Agency REA(2)

Funded by the European Union

SALTOpower
Creating Innovative Energy Solutions
Geração de energia elétrica solar · Évora · 276 seguidores · 2-10 funcionários

João e mais 68 conexões seguem esta página

Envie mensagem Seguindo

Início Sobre Publicações Vagas Pessoas

SALTOpower
276 seguidores
1 m

● SALTOpower International Symposium discusses the role of molten salt technologies ...mais

Exibir tradução

 SALTOpower International Symposium discusses the role of molten salt technologies
saltopower.uevora.pt

● Dominique Livreiro e mais 6 pessoas

👤 Gostei 💬 Comentar ➦ Compartilhar ✉ Enviar

Publicação removida Desfazer

Agradecemos o seu feedback.

SALTOpower
276 seguidores
1 m

● Germany: International Symposium discusses the role of molten salt technologies

The event brought together experts, policymakers, researchers and industry ...mais

Exibir tradução

 Germany: International Symposium discusses the role of molten salt technologies
saltopower.uevora.pt

SALTOpower
276 seguidores
1 m

● Italy: International Symposium discusses the role of molten salt technologies

The event brought together experts, policymakers, researchers and industry ...mais

Exibir tradução

 Italy: International Symposium discusses the role of molten salt technologies
saltopower.uevora.pt

● 4

👤 Gostei 💬 Comentar ➦ Compartilhar ✉ Enviar

SALTOpower
276 seguidores
2 m

● The 6th SALTOpower Project Meeting took place in Rome, from 27 to 28 of May 2025 ...mais

Exibir tradução

 Project Meeting #6 in Rome
saltopower.uevora.pt

● Paula Martins e mais 7 pessoas 2 compartilhamentos

👤 Gostei 💬 Comentar ➦ Compartilhar ✉ Enviar

SALTOpower
276 seguidores
2 m

💧 Prêmios de Inovação ENERH2O

A 3ª edição da ENERH2O - Energy and Water Innovation & Technology terá ...mais

 PRÊMIO ENERH2O - enerh2o
enerh2o.com

● Dominique Livreiro e mais 1 pessoa

👤 Gostei 💬 Comentar ➦ Compartilhar ✉ Enviar

SALTOpower
276 seguidores
11 m

● Meet Our Team

● Matteo Battaglia - PhD student of University of Rome TorVergata ...mais

Exibir tradução

MEET OUR TEAM

Matteo Battaglia

● **YouTube**

Renewable Energies Chair

@RenewableEnergiesChair · 17 subscribers · 22 videos

The RE Chair aims at developing technological solutions and Solar energy applications for...more

catedraer.uevora.pt and 1 more link

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Consortium and Project Objectives
11 videos

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View full playlist

SALTOpower
Introduction
13 videos

SALTOpower
View full playlist

SALTOpower
Renewable Energies Chair - 1/13

↻ ↺ ⋮

- SALTOpower FTS#1 Day1 Session1**
Renewable Energies Chair
46:14
- SALTOpower FTS#1 Day1 Session2**
Renewable Energies Chair
59:38
- SALTOpower FTS#1 Day2 Session1**
Renewable Energies Chair
1:20:25
- SALTOpower FTS#1 Day2 Session2**
Renewable Energies Chair
1:35:15
- Gender Equality Seminar #1**
Renewable Energies Chair
1:01:18
- SALTOpower FTS#2 - Day 1 Session 1**
Renewable Energies Chair
2:54:49
- SALTOpower FTS#2 - Day 1 Session 2**
Renewable Energies Chair
1:51:50
- SALTOpower FTS#2 - Day 2**
Renewable Energies Chair
50:12
- SALTOpower Fast Track School #3**

● **Instagram**

Quais são as novidades?

SALTOpower - Creating Innovative Energy Solutions

95 publicações 70 seguidores 58 a seguir

European Facility on Molten SALT technologies TO power and energy system applications
GA Number: 101079303
European Research Executive Agency REA.C3
www.youtube.com/watch?v=YBW9lcAKtL0 e m...

Painel Profissional
895 visualizações nos últimos 30 dias.

Editar perfil Partilhar perfil

APPENDIX 5: NEWSLETTER

- Newsletter #1 - <https://mailchi.mp/329ab7aa3cea/newsletter-1>
- Newsletter #2 - <https://us17.campaign-archive.com/?u=531ca5d6f811a1d142314b9d8&id=fcc014caa9>
- Newsletter #3 - <https://mailchi.mp/54114242f502/newsletter-13946914>
- Newsletter #4 - <https://mailchi.mp/b6addba2c396/newsletter-14155086>
- Newsletter #5 - <https://mailchi.mp/d3bd552d6c5d/newsletter-14164223>
- Newsletter #6 - <https://mailchi.mp/bc37d5b8a222/newsletter-14166038>
- Newsletter #7 - <https://mailchi.mp/f04b06484523/newsletter-14168402>
- Newsletter #8 - <https://mailchi.mp/14c4de7ac19d/newsletter-14170369>
- Newsletter “Energy Strategy” Symposium - <https://mailchi.mp/d1a49c317bec/newsletter-14171674>
- Newsletter #9 - <https://mailchi.mp/7d3adb4416c2/newsletter-14172826>
- Newsletter #10 - <https://mailchi.mp/f993d0d19acf/newsletter-14174797>
- Newsletter #11 - <https://mailchi.mp/0d2a6a13f4ef/newsletter-14176843>
- Newsletter #12 - <https://mailchi.mp/3d415542c0a3/newsletter-14178246>

APPENDIX 6: PRESS RELEASES

- **Energy Strategy Symposium press release and media publications links**

Universidade de Évora recebe especialistas do setor da energia no simpósio nacional “Energy Strategy”

Évora, 3 de fevereiro de 2025 – A Universidade de Évora será palco, no próximo dia 13 de fevereiro, do simpósio nacional “Energy Strategy”, promovido pela Cátedra de Energias Renováveis no âmbito do projeto europeu [SALTOpower](#).

Este projeto resulta de uma parceria entre a Universidade de Évora, a Agência Aeroespacial Alemã (DLR) e a Agência Italiana para a Energia Nuclear e Renováveis (ENEA).

O evento reunirá especialistas, decisores políticos, investigadores e representantes da indústria para debater o impacto das tecnologias de Sais Fundidos para aplicações no setor energético. O objetivo é promover uma reflexão sobre o potencial contributo destas tecnologias para os objetivos do Plano Nacional de Energia e Clima, o desenvolvimento industrial e o crescimento de exportações associadas à sua implementação.

As atividades terão início às 09h15, na Casa Cordovil da Universidade de Évora. Durante a tarde, os participantes terão a oportunidade de visitar a Évora Molten Salt Platform, no pólo de Évora da [INIESC](#) (Infraestrutura Nacional de Investigação em Energia Solar de Concentração). Esta infraestrutura integra o Consórcio Europeu de Infraestrutura de Investigação ERIC EU-SOLARIS e é um centro de excelência em investigação e desenvolvimento de tecnologias de sais fundidos.

Informações sobre o Evento

Data: 13 de fevereiro de 2025

Hora: 9h15

Local: Casa Cordovil, Universidade de Évora, Évora
(<https://maps.app.goo.gl/DLx3vTe29B6znqr16>)

Évora Molten Salt Platform (<https://maps.app.goo.gl/3hqvRp3GkVB1QQL46>)

Para obter mais informações, por favor contacte:

Joana Mouquinho Penderlico - joana.penderlico@uevora.pt

Dominique Livreiro - dominique.livreiro@uevora.pt

Media publications:

- <https://diariodosul.pt/2025/02/06/universidade-de-evora-recebe-especialistas-no-simp-osio-nacional-energy-strategy/>
- https://regiao-sul.pt/ambiente/universidade-de-evora-recebe-especialistas-no-simposio-nacional-energy-strategy/699913#google_vignette
- <https://adefesa.org/2025/02/05/jornal-a-defesa-29-de-janeiro-de-2025-edicao-impressa/>
- *Accumulo termico per decarbonizzare l’industria*, article by ENEA media publication

- **Before ENERH2O - Trade Show press release and media publications links**

Projetos da Cátedra de Energias Renováveis da UÉvora marcam presença na feira internacional ENERH2O

Nos dias 24 e 25 de setembro de 2025, a Cátedra de Energias Renováveis da Universidade de Évora (CER-UÉ) estará presente na 3ª edição da ENERH2O – Energy & Water Innovation & Technology Trade Show, na Exponor, Porto.

Este é um dos principais eventos profissionais dedicados à inovação nos setores da energia e da gestão da água. O encontro reúne empresas, instituições, investigadores e startups para debater soluções tecnológicas e apresentar projetos que respondem aos grandes desafios da transição energética e da sustentabilidade.

A CER-UÉ irá marcar presença com os projetos Twinning, SALTOpower e Sol2H2O, ambos Horizonte Europa. Os Twinning terão um papel de destaque numa das conferências do evento, denominada: "Apresentação dos projetos europeus Sol2H2O and SALTOpower: Technology, research, and value chain". Estes projetos assumem-se como exemplos de como a ciência e a tecnologia podem apoiar a competitividade das empresas e contribuir para uma matriz energética mais sustentável.

A ENERH2O contará ainda com uma conferência promovida pela Aliança para a Transição Energética (ATE), que reunirá especialistas para debater os caminhos da transição energética em Portugal. Um dos convidados será o Dr. Pedro Horta, coordenador da unidade SOL4R.

Com um programa diversificado, a ENERH2O afirma-se como um espaço privilegiado de encontro entre academia, indústria e entidades públicas, promovendo networking, transferência de conhecimento e parcerias estratégicas. A participação da CER-UÉ e dos seus projetos sublinha o papel da investigação científica na construção de soluções inovadoras para os desafios energéticos e ambientais que marcam o presente e moldam o futuro.

Media publications:

- https://odigital.sapo.pt/projetos-da-universidade-de-evora-em-destaque-na-feira-internacional-enerh2o/#google_vignette
- <https://www.rederural.gov.pt/pt/projetos-relevantes?view=article&id=8511:universidad-e-de-evora-leva-inovacao-energetica-e-hidrica-a-feira-enerh2o-no-porto&catid=12>

- **Fast-Track Schools press release and media publications links**

Fast-Track Schools do [SALTOpower](#) capacitam jovens investigadores

O projeto europeu [SALTOpower](#), financiado pelo Horizonte Europa, concluiu com sucesso um ciclo de três Fast-Track Schools que reuniram jovens investigadores, estudantes de doutoramento e especialistas da indústria para explorar o papel das tecnologias de sais fundidos no armazenamento de energia renovável.

As formações decorreram nos três países que fazem parte do consórcio - Itália, Alemanha e Portugal - e abordaram desde os fundamentos científicos até à aplicação prática e ao potencial de mercado destas tecnologias:

Roma, Itália - *Solar-driven water production & water treatment technologies and brine treatment processes*

Colónia, Alemanha - *Molten Salt technologies and energy system applications*

Évora, Portugal – *Molten Salt use cases, risks, bankability and new approaches*

Com mais de 100 inscrições e participação ativa, tanto presencial como online, as Fast-Track Schools superaram as expectativas de adesão e impacto. Os resultados das avaliações revelam uma taxa média de satisfação de 4,3 em 5, refletindo a relevância dos temas e a qualidade da formação.

Os participantes tiveram a oportunidade de interagir com investigadores seniores e jovens talentos do consórcio, envolvendo instituições como a Universidade de Évora, DLR (Alemanha), [ENEA](#) (Itália) e parceiros industriais. Para além das apresentações, destacaram-se visitas a infraestruturas de investigação de referência e sessões de brainstorming, onde os jovens investigadores tiveram um papel ativo na discussão e construção de ideias.

As tecnologias de sais fundidos desempenham um papel central no desenvolvimento de soluções de armazenamento térmico de energia, essenciais para garantir a integração de energias renováveis de forma estável e competitiva. Para além da sua aplicação consolidada em centrais solares de concentração (CSP), os sais fundidos estão a abrir caminho para novos setores, como calor de processo industrial e baterias térmicas tipo Carnot.

Todos os materiais das Fast-Track Schools, incluindo apresentações e gravações, estão disponíveis online:

[Website SALTOpower](#)

Media publications:

- <https://odigital.sapo.pt/evora-jovens-investigadores-capacitados-em-energias-renovaveis-e-solucoes-solares-para-a-agua/>
- <https://regiao-sul.pt/educacao-e-ciencia/capitacao-de-jovens-investigadores-em-transicao-energetica-e-agua/732415>

- **After ENERH2O - Trade Show press release and media publications links**

SOL4R e INIESC levam inovação em energias renováveis à ENERH2O 2025

A SOL4R Applied Research in Solar Energy for the Energy Transition (FCT UID 6478) marcou presença na 3ª edição da ENERH2O – Energy & Water Innovation & Technology Trade Show, que decorreu nos dias 24 e 25 de setembro de 2025 na Exponor, no Porto.

Os projetos SALTOpower e Sol2H2O, coordenados pela Universidade de Évora, tiveram um papel de destaque, mostrando o que de melhor se faz no âmbito da energia solar para onexo água-energia e nas tecnologias de sais fundidos para aplicações energéticas. Esta participação revelou-se uma mais-valia, pois permitiu divulgar o trabalho desenvolvido, estabelecer contactos com empresas e profissionais do setor e abrir caminho a possíveis sinergias futuras que reforcem a ligação entre investigação e mercado.

No quadro das conferências do certame, o coordenador da unidade SOL4R, Pedro Horta, apresentou uma conferência dedicada às temáticas “Sol2H2O: The potential role of Solar Energy in the Water-Energy Nexus” e “Molten Salt technologies as an Energy Hub for the Energy Transition”, relacionadas com ambos os projetos, na qual foi apresentada a Infraestrutura Nacional de Investigação em Energia Solar de Concentração (INIESC) e as atividades inovadoras da SOL4R no Pólo da Mitra em Évora. Participou também na sessão promovida pela Aliança para a Transição Energética, contribuindo para o debate sobre o hidrogénio verde e o seu papel na transição energética.

Com esta presença, a SOL4R e a INIESC consolidaram a sua posição no panorama nacional de investigação em energia solar, reforçando o seu compromisso com o desenvolvimento de soluções tecnológicas sustentáveis.

O evento reuniu cerca de uma centena de empresas dos setores energético e da água de Portugal e Espanha e contou com cerca de 40 conferências dedicadas à inovação nos domínios da energia e da água.

Media publications:

- <https://www.agroportal.pt/ue-leva-inovacao-a-enerh2o/>

APPENDIX 6: ROLL-UP AND BROCHURES

Consortium

UNIVERSIDADE DE ÉVORA

Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt
German Aerospace Center

Italian National Agency for New Technologies, Energy and Sustainable Economic Development

Creating Innovative Energy Solutions

Funded by the European Union
Grant Number: 101019120
European Research Council Horizon Europe

Funded by the European Union
Grant Number: 101019120
European Research Council Horizon Europe

Funded by the European Union
Grant Number: 101019120
European Research Council Horizon Europe

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 LinkedIn: /company/saltpower/
 YouTube: @RenewableEnergiesChair
 Instagram: @saltpower_heurope

Subscribe our Newsletter

SALTOpower

European Facility on Molten SALT Technologies TO power and energy system applications

November 2022 - October 2025

Funded by the European Union
Grant Number: 101019120
European Research Council Horizon Europe

The Project Concept

The combination of Thermal Energy Storage with Concentrated Solar Power (CSP) is a key solution for producing dispatchable electricity. While thermal oil systems were the standard in early CSP plants, Molten Salts (MS) are now emerging as the preferred heat transfer and storage medium.

Research on MS has advanced in Germany and Italy, supported by specialized Research Infrastructures (RI). With the recent launch of a full-scale Molten Salt Solar system in Évora, Portugal has joined this research with a significant new RI.

This proposal aims to leverage the expertise of two established European partners and the new RI in a Widening country to enhance scientific excellence and innovation in MS technologies. SALTOpower has the goal of establishing a leading European facility for developing and testing MS-based energy storage and power solutions, integrating various renewable energy sources with power and gas grids.

Funded by the European Union
Grant Number: 101019120
European Research Council Horizon Europe

Funded by the European Union
Grant Number: 101019120
European Research Council Horizon Europe

Funded by the European Union
Grant Number: 101019120
European Research Council Horizon Europe

Key Objectives

Engaging two top-class leading partners around a scientific strategy for stepping up and stimulating scientific excellence and innovation capacity on the use of Molten Salt technologies as a Key Clean Energy Transition solution, SALTOpower aims at enhanced networking with the Coordinator Widening partner, establishing the Reference European Facility in Molten Salt Research for Energy applications.

1. To raise UÉvora research profile by means of cutting-edge research with EU top-class leading partners DLR and ENEA;
2. To raise the research, technical and administrative skills of UÉvora staff;
3. To steer Career Building and attractiveness of Young Researchers to UÉvora;
4. To enhance the networking of UÉvora in scientific and Industry fora;
5. To ensure the valorisation and impact of UÉvora research.

Living in Alentejo

www.saltpower.uevora.pt/living-in-alentejo

Mentoring Program

SALTOpower has a Mentoring Program that offers the opportunity to participate as either a mentor or a mentee in activities outside of work. If you are interested in signing up, simply fill out the forms.

Join us!

SALTOpower

Creating Innovative Energy Solutions

European facility on Molten SALT technologies
TO power and energy system applications

UNIVERSIDADE DE ÉVORA

Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt
German Aerospace Center

European National Agency for Research, Technology, Energy and Sustainable Economic Development

Funded by the European Union

European Facility on Molten SALT technologies TO power and energy system applications
GA Number: [101079303](#)
European Research Executive Agency REA-C3

APPENDIX 7: SOCIAL MEDIA, NEWSLETTER, WEBSITE AND ZENODO NUMBERS THROUGHOUT THE PROJECT

- Social media followers

Date	LinkedIn	X	Instagram	YouTube	Total	KPI's - good	KPI's - very good	KPI's - excellent
M1 - nov 2022						200-400	400-600	>600
M2								
M3								
M4	0	0	0	0	0			
M5	0							
M6	12				12			
M7	38				38			
M8	40				40			
M9	39				39			
M10 - aug 2023	42				42			
M11	47	3	18	0	68			
M12	62	3	23	7	95			
M13 - nov 2023	69	4	43	87	203			
M14	78	6	46	107	237			
M15					0			
M16 - feb 2024	105	42	56	115	318			
M17	133	42	60	126	361			
M18	175	56	64	138	433			
M19	194	56	66	146	462			
M20 - jun 2024	204	64	66	161	495			
M21	217	60	70	261	608			
M22	218	65	68	319	670			
M23	228	58	67	338	691			
M24 - out 24	238	57	68	370	733			
M25	242	33	68	435	778			
M26	243	14	68	470	795			
M27	250	14	69	487	820			
M28	259	13	69	581	922			
M29	263	12	71	629	975			
M30 - apr 2025	263	12	70	642	987			
M31	266	12	73	656	1007			
M32	273	0	72	664	1009			
M33	275	0	72	701	1048			
M34	276	0	71	726	1073			
M35					0			
M36 - oct 2025					0			

- Newsletter subscribers

Date	Subscribers	KPI's - good	KPI's - very good	KPI's - excellent
M1 - nov 2022				
M2				
M3				
M4				
M5				
M6				
M7				
M8		100-200	200-400	>400
M9				
M10 - aug 2023				
M11	31			
M12	89			#1
M13	100			
M14	100			#2
M15				
M16 - feb 2024	105			#3
M17	108			
M18	110			#4
M19	121			
M20 - jun 2024	118			#5
M21	132			
M22	130			#6
M23	130			
M24	130			#7
M25	136			
M26	136			#8
M27	139			#Simpósio
M28 - fev 25	161			#9
M29	161			
M30 - apr 2025	160			#10
M31	160			
M32	163			#11
M33	164			
M34	164			#12
M35				
M36 - oct 2025				

- Website visitors and visualizations

Date	Visitors	KPI's - good	KPI's - very good	KPI's - excellent	
M1 - nov 2022		1000-2000	2000-3000	>3000	
M2					
M3					
M4					
M5					
M6					
M7					
M8					
M9					
M10 - aug 2023					
M11	91				new website
M12	131				
M13	179				
M14	229				
M15	262				
M16 - feb 2024	322				
M17	428				
M18	522				
M19	583				
M20 - jun 2024	659				visualizations: 2081
M21	790				visualizations: 2426
M22	878				visualizations: 2650
M23	986				visualizations: 2845
M24	1102				visualizations: 3081
M25	1187				visualizations: 3304
M26	1259				visualizations: 3455
M27	1366				visualizations: 3684
M28	1486				visualizations: 3950
M29	1556				visualizations: 4128
M30 - apr 2025	1592				visualizations: 4232
M31	1743				visualizations: 4425
M32	1745				visualizations: 4568
M33	1839				visualizations: 4792
M34	1870				visualizations: 4916
M35					
M36 - oct 2025					

- Zenodo downloads

Date	Downloads	KPI's - good	PI's - very good	PI's - excellent	
M1 - nov 2022			10	30	50
M2					
M3					
M4					
M5					
M6					
M7 - may 2023					1st publication
M8					
M9					
M10 - aug 2023					
M11					
M12	2				
M13					
M14					
M15					
M16 - feb 2024					
M17					
M18					
M19	197				
M20 - jun 2024	222				
M21	383				
M22	552				
M23	679				
M24	727				
M25	835				
M26	1196				
M27	1305				
M28	1720				
M29	1921				
M30 - apr 2025	2083				
M31	2473				
M32	2598	59 c/ acknowledgement			
M33	3106	67 c/ acknowledgement			
M34	3413	72 c/ acknowledgement	215 deliverables	466 papers	
M35					
M36 - oct 2025					